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Leveraging Hierarchical Classification and Thumbnail Injection for Improved Weed and Crop Detection

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Computer Vision in Biosystems

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Preface

This master thesis, "Leveraging Hierarchical Classification and Thumbnail Injection for Improved Weed and Crop Detection" is written by Michael Søndergaard Nørbo Madsen, student at Aarhus University studying a Master of Science in Computer Engineering. This thesis was completed during the period from 29 January 2024 to 04 June 2024 and accounts for 30 ECTS.

The research presented in this thesis was conducted in collaboration with the "Computer Vision in Biosystems" research group at Aarhus University and I-GIS, a company specializing in precision agriculture tools for weed management. The study focuses on enhancing the performance of I-GIS's YOLOv5 object detection model, "CropWeed", which is integrated into their RoboWeedMaPS platform for analyzing field images and generating targeted spray maps for farmers.

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A declaration of the use of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) is included in Appendix A.7.

Michael Søndergaard Nørbo Madsen
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Abstract

In precision agriculture, accurate weed and crop recognition is essential for effective management practices. However, existing methods face challenges such as class imbalance, where categories like "Monocot" and "Dicot" dominate, and the under-utilization of annotated data in partially approved images. This thesis presents two strategies to address these challenges, enhancing the performance of I-GIS's YOLOv5 object detection model, CropWeed, for weed and crop identification.

The first approach involves implementing a hierarchical classification method through the CropDiva model framework, which refines broad "Monocot" and "Dicot" labels into more specific classes. By training CropDiva on a subset of the RoboWeedMaPS dataset and applying strict prediction confidence thresholds for each class, 26.7% of "Dicot" thumbnails were confidently re-labeled into more specific classes, effectively reducing class imbalance without requiring manual re-annotation.

The second approach introduces a novel Thumbnail Injection Framework designed to utilize approved thumbnails from partially annotated images. This proposed framework integrates these approved thumbnails from unused images into fully approved images while avoiding overlaps. Evaluation results indicate that the injected dataset improved the YOLOv5 model's mean Average Precision (mAP) by 12-49% for four out of five targeted classes with limited data.

The key contributions of this thesis include demonstrating the effectiveness of hierarchical classification for label refinement and developing a robust framework for data augmentation from partial annotations. The proposed methods significantly enhance the YOLOv5 model's performance on specific weed and crop classes, providing insights for future research in similar precision agriculture settings.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context and Motivation

Global demand for agricultural products is increasing rapidly as the world's population is estimated to grow to almost 10 billion by 2050, according to a report from the United States Government Accountability Office (GAO) released in January 2024[1]. However, farmers face challenges in meeting these rising demands due to factors like:

- A shrinking agricultural workforce
- Environmental impacts
- Rising production costs

To target these factors, precision agriculture has emerged as an essential practice in modern farming to address the global food demand while simultaneously mitigating environmental challenges by promoting an efficient agricultural production, which is done through precise resource management and a data-driven approach to farming[2].

A key aspect of precision agriculture is the ability to accurately recognize and differentiate between different types of crops and weeds. Weeds pose a significant threat to global crop production, causing potential yield losses of up to 43% worldwide[3]. Technologies like targeted spray systems and automated mechanical weeders utilize computer vision techniques and machine learning algorithms to identify weeds, allowing for precise herbicide application or physical weed removal while avoiding damage to the crops. By minimizing herbicide use, these precision agriculture technologies benefit the environment by preventing excessive chemicals from entering the soil and water-flows, while also being economically beneficial to farmers by reducing the cost of inputs[4].

The development of robust weed and crop recognition systems is essential for the widespread transition to precision agriculture practices amongst farmers. However, the creation of such systems presents several challenges, including the need for large annotated datasets, variability of field conditions, and the hierarchical nature of plant species[5].

The research group, Computer Vision in Biosystems[6], at Aarhus University (AU) collaborates with I-GIS, a company developing precision agriculture tools for weed management, to enhance agricultural practices through modern technology practices. I-GIS possesses a large dataset of real field images captured from real farming operations across Denmark. These images contain various plants,

including crops and weeds, and are stored and accessible in the platform, RoboWeedMaPS (RWM). This is how RoboWeedMaPS is described by the Computer Vision in Biosystems research group on their website:

"In RoboWeedMaPS the aim is to bridge the gap between the potential herbicide savings and the required weed inspections by using image analysis for automating the weed inspection part"[7]

Images captured, consisting of weeds, crops, and other field elements, are uploaded to this platform, where they are analyzed using a YOLOv5 model, named CropWeed, to identify and classify the present plant instances. Using the tools provided by RoboWeedMaPS, farmers can view generated maps of their fields and export spray-maps for targeted spray control, optimizing herbicide usage and improving crop management.

Patriotisk Selskab, a company collaborating with I-GIS, uses the RoboWeedMaPS platform to provide targeted weed control services to farmers. They capture field images using an ATV equipped with advanced cameras, which continuously take close-up images of the emerging crops and weeds. Using the RoboWeedMaPS technology, they can map and identify weed species from the cotyledon stage. As stated on their website:

"We have seen savings of 50-80% of the usual herbicide use with spot-spraying of selected agents after our weed mapping and species determination"[8]

This results in substantial environmental benefits, as well as economic benefits for the farmers.

1.2 Problem Statement

A key limitation faced by I-GIS is that their YOLOv5 model, CropWeed, is trained solely on images where all annotations are approved, explicitly or implicitly. This excludes a significant portion of the dataset where images that contain a mix of approved and unapproved annotations are excluded, resulting in a large amount of data being under-utilized. Additionally, the model struggles with accurately classifying less frequent weed species due to the dominance of the broad Monocot and Dicot classes in the training data. This class imbalance hinders the model's ability to generalize well and accurately identify specific weed species, which is crucial for effective targeted weed control.

Another critical challenge is the hierarchical nature of plant species classification. Many weeds and crops are broadly categorized into the Monocot and Dicot classes, which merely denotes whether the plant has one or two cotyledons[9]. These classes are the least detailed levels in a hierarchical sense, but have the highest representation in the RoboWeedMaPS database. However, for effective

weed management and precise herbicide application, it is essential to classify weeds and crops at a more specific classes. Enhancing the specificity of these classifications can significantly improve the accuracy and effectiveness of the YOLO model. Going forward, I-GIS and Patriotisk Selskab[10], have made a wishlist mapping of specific classes that they want the model to recognize more accurately.

In parallel to these challenges, the Computer Vision in Biosystems group at AU has developed CropDiva, which is a classification model framework specifically tailored for crop and weed classification. CropDiva is trained on individual plant images extracted from full field images (bounding boxes). These images are labeled using standardized Plant EPO codes, a widely adopted coding system for plants and pests. Despite a good performing system, the current YOLOv5 model trained and used by I-GIS has limitations in accurately classifying a diverse range of weed species, which will be the main focus of this thesis. The primary challenges for bettering the model is identified as the following problems:

- **Manual Annotation:** the need for extensive manual annotation of field images is time-consuming and prone to errors
- **Hierarchical Classification:** the broad classification categories (Monocot and Dicot) overshadow more specific weed classes, limiting the model's accuracy
- **Data Utilization:** a significant portion of the RoboWeedMaPS dataset consists of partially approved images that cannot be used for training, leading to under-utilization of available data

1.3 Research Questions and Goals

This thesis is driven by the following research questions, which address the core challenges identified:

- **RQ1:** *How can a hierarchical classification approach, utilizing a trained classification model (CropDiva), be leveraged to refine the labels of the "Monocot" and "Dicot" classes in the existing dataset, thereby increasing the representation of more specific weed classes without manually revisiting each image?*
- **RQ2:** *Which methodologies can be developed to utilize the approved thumbnails from images not approved for YOLO training (despite containing approved bounding boxes)? The goal is to enhance the dataset's richness and diversity while maintaining accuracy in object detection.*

By exploring these research questions, this thesis aims to investigate novel approaches to address the challenges of class imbalance and data under-utilization in the context of weed and crop recognition. The thesis will focus on leveraging

the I-GIS dataset, the YOLOv5 model (CropWeed), and AU's CropDiva model framework to gain insights into improving the precision and effectiveness of weed and crop recognition systems, aiming to ultimately support better precision agriculture practices. The exploration of these research questions will involve:

- Investigating the potential of the AU CropDiva model for refining weed labels through hierarchical classification of the Monocot and Dicot classes
- Developing and evaluating methodologies to augment the dataset using the unused approved thumbnails from partially approved images
- Examining the impact of these approaches on the performance of I-GIS YOLOv5 model in practical settings utilizing the wishlist classes

Chapter 2

Background and Related Works

This chapter provides an overview of the key technologies and methodologies used in precision agriculture, particularly focusing on weed and crop recognition. Additionally, it reviews related works to existing challenges to identify research gaps that this thesis aims to address.

2.1 Precision Agriculture and Weed/Crop Recognition

A wide variety of technologies are integrated in precision agriculture to optimize farming practices with the purpose of improving crop yield, reducing environmental impact, and increasing sustainability in general. This section provides a brief overview over key technologies in precision agriculture with focus on the specific role of weed and crop recognition within precision agriculture, highlighting the relevant technologies and methods used.

2.1.1 Overview of Key Technologies Used in Precision Agriculture

Precision agriculture is a data-driven approach, meaning it relies on the gathering and processing of farming data. Farming data is analyzed on individual, temporal, and spatial levels, which ensures accuracy and precision[11]. Some of the key technologies that precision agriculture relies on are:

- **Global Positioning System (GPS):** enabling precise mapping and navigation in fields
- **Remote Sensing:** utilizing satellite and aerial imagery (e.g. drones) for large-scale crop monitoring
- **IoT Sensors:** gathering and monitoring real-time data on soil conditions, moisture levels, and plant health
- **Variable Rate Technology (VRT):** adjusting input application (e.g. fertilizers, herbicides) based on field-specific needs
- **Machine Learning:** analyze data to provide insights for crop management

2.1.2 Weed and Crop Recognition in Precision Agriculture

Weeds compete with crops for nutrients, water, and light, potentially leading to significant yield losses[12]. Traditional broad-spectrum herbicide applications are not only inefficient, but they are also harmful to the environment. However, applying herbicides only where it is needed can significantly reduce the herbicide

usage while also minimizing the environmental pollution and improving the economic efficiency for farmers[5]. Therefore, accurate weed/crop recognition is crucial in precision agriculture because it enables targeted weed control.

The field of machine learning and computer vision have revolutionized precision agriculture by providing techniques and algorithms that can enable precise identification of weeds and crops. Utilizing machine learning algorithms, automated systems can differentiate between crops and weeds, which in turn enables targeted weed control measure that offers significant benefits over traditional broad-spectrum herbicide applications. Bettering these methods of differentiating between specific species of crops and weeds even further provides better targeted weed control, which not only reduce the amount of herbicide used, but also minimizes the risk of weed populations developing herbicide resistance[13].

2.1.3 Traditional Weed and Crop Recognition

Traditionally, weed and crop recognition involved visual inspection and hand weeding by farmers or agronomists. This has been the standard of weed management for a long time, and while this can be sufficient for smaller farms, it becomes very impractical, time-consuming, and error-prone for large farms where time-sensitive and accurate identification of weeds is critical for effective management[13].

2.2 Image Processing and Object detection

Due to the limitations of manual methods, image processing techniques has been widely adopted for automating weed and crop recognition. Image processing techniques utilizes algorithms to analyze digital images and extract features that distinguish crops from weeds or specific species of weeds or crops from eachother. The common image processing techniques used in weed and crop recognition include[14]:

- **Pre-processing:** these techniques can better the quality of raw images which is used to improve analysis accuracy:
 - **Background removal:** separating the foreground (plant in this context) from the background, which reduces noise and focuses analysis on relevant part of the image
 - **Image enhancement:** includes methods like adjusting contrast or sharpness, which makes relevant features more distinct
 - **Image resizing:** this involves adjusting the size of the collected images to a standard resolution, which can help in maintaining consistency across the dataset and ensuring that the images are suitable for processing by machine learning models

- **Segmentation:** involves dividing an image into segments to isolate regions of interest, which could be distinguishing plants from the background or separating crops and weeds
- **Feature extraction:** this involves identifying and extracting key characteristics of plants, e.g. shape, color, and texture, which can assist in distinguishing between different species

These techniques (especially segmentation and feature extraction) are central for computer vision techniques, which are machine learning approaches that in this domain can help recognize weeds and crops.

2.2.1 Machine Learning Approaches

Machine learning approaches has gained a significant amount of tracking in recent years as a powerful tool for computer vision tasks in general, especially deep learning, which offers an increased accuracy and adaptability compared to traditional image processing and manual methods in weed/crop recognition. While traditional machine learning methods can be used to learn from data and make decisions based on observed patterns, features of interest are often hand-crafted by humans, which can be a hard task - as well as a non-optimal solution - in regards to recognizing weeds or crops. Therefore, especially deep learning has gained traction.

Deep learning uses deep neural networks, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to learn the feature representations for different classes from the raw images themselves. These networks are excel at extracting relevant features at different scales, which is desirable in weed/crop recognition tasks. Examples of widely used CNN architectures are VGGNet, ResNet, EfficientDet, AlexNet, and InceptionNet[14].

2.2.1.1 Classification and Object Detection

Another computer vision technique that uses deep learning is object detection models, which are designed to both localize and classify objects in images. Unlike classification models that assign a single label to an entire image, object detection models are capable of both identifying and locating objects within a single image. This is achieved by predicting both bounding boxes (boxes that encompass each detected object), and class labels for each bounding box, denoting the object. In weed and crop recognition, object detection models are especially viable, since they are capable of locating and classifying multiple plants in an image, which is almost always the case in images of real fields. Figure 2.1 illustrates the differences between classification and object detection using a real field image with weeds and crops.

The *You Only Look Once* (YOLO) series of object detection models are popular choices in precision agriculture due to them being able to run in real-time with

(a) Classification: entire image is assigned one label: "field", "plants", "dirt" (b) Object detection: each plant is detected and assigned an individual label

Figure 2.1: Comparison of classification and object detection in field images

high accuracy, which are desirable properties when detecting and differentiating crops and weeds, potentially enabling immediate actions in the field.

2.3 Object Detection with YOLO

There exists numerous versions of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) object detection framework. This section will present the YOLO series and its evolution of models, focusing especially on the YOLOv5 architecture, since it is used by RoboWeedMaPS.

2.3.1 Overview of YOLO (You Only Look Once)

The YOLO object detection framework[15] revolutionized the computer field by introducing a real-time and single-stage objection detection model. Unlike two-stage architectures like R-CNN variations, which required a Region Proposal Network and subsequent classification, YOLO directly predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities in a single forward pass. This single-stage approach significantly improved both speed and accuracy from previous models.

YOLO achieves its single-stage detection through a grid cell mechanism, in which the input image is divided into a grid of cells, illustrated in Figure 2.2. Each cell is responsible for detecting objects whose centers are within that cell. With this approach, object localization (predicting bounding box coordinates) can be computed for each cell simultaneously, enabling parallel processing, which is key in YOLO's speed and efficiency.

Figure 2.2: Illustration of grid cells in YOLO

2.3.1.1 Evolution from YOLOv1 to YOLOv8

The YOLO architecture has evolved through several iterations since debut by Joseph Redmon in 2015. Each iteration has introduced improvements, pushing the boundaries of real-time object detection performance. The YOLO models are made by different groups of people and organizations, however the official YOLO models mainly stem from the same original authors: Joseph Redmon, Ali Farhadi, and later Alexey Bochkovskiy. Below is a brief overview of the different models and their key advancements:

- **YOLOv1[15]**: the original YOLO model by Joseph Redmon introduced the single-stage approach by modelling object detection as a single regression problem instead of a two-headed regression and classification problem.
- **YOLOv2 (YOLO9000)[16]**: this version was introduced by Joseph Redmon and Ali Farhadi, which included a new network architecture (Darknet-19) that used batch normalization and anchor boxes to achieve higher accuracy and faster speeds.
- **YOLOv3[17]**: this version by Joseph Redmon and Ali Farhadi introduced multi-scale detection detection with three detection layers, which allowed for better detection of objects of various sizes, as well as using the more complex Darknet-53 architecture.
- **YOLOv4[18]**: this version was developed by Alexey Bochkovskiy et. al., and further increased the performance by implementing a mosaic augmentation technique that combines four training images into one, as well as introducing the Mish activation function, CIoU loss for better bounding box regression, and the CSPDarknet53 backbone architecture.
- **YOLOv5[19]**: this version was developed by Glenn Jocher and the Ultralytics team, and did not use the it was the first version written

in PyTorch[20]. Therefore this version was the first to not use the Darknet framework, instead using PyTorch to make a more flexible and efficient framework that supported transfer learning, various model sizes (nano, small, medium, large, extra-large), and improving the overall training and inference speed. Despite not being created by any of the original authors, YOLOv5 was widely acceptance due to its improved usability, performance, and the strong community and support from Ultralytics.

- **YOLOv6[21]**: this version was developed by Meituan et. al. intended for industrial applications. However, this version is not widely regarded as a part of the official YOLO series, as it was not developed by any of the original authors - possibly due to less community involvement.
- **YOLOv7[22]**: this version was developed by Alexey Bochkovskiy et. al., and continued the development line from YOLOv4, maintaining a closer connection to the original development path and therefore accepted as a part of the official series. They introduced new features, including bag-of-freebies (BoF) and bag-of-specials (BoS) techniques that optimized performance with only a minimal additional cost in computation.
- **YOLOv8[23]**: this version was also developed by Glenn Jocher and Ultralytics, building upon the success of YOLOv5. Ultralytics has made themselves a significant contributor to the YOLO series, making their YOLOv8 model a natural progression in the series. YOLOv8 included a new backbone architecture, a more efficient neck, and an anchor-free detection mechanism, which increased both the accuracy and speed.

This constant evolution of the YOLO framework is evident, pushing the boundaries of real-time object detection with every iteration. A note to takeaway from this is that utilizing newer YOLO models, when given the choice, seems to often provide an advantage. As later iterations tend to utilize the current state-of-the-art techniques, this could lead to improvements in both accuracy and efficiency.

2.3.2 YOLOv5

As I-GIS trains and infers a YOLOv5 for weed/crop recognition in their precision agriculture system, RoboWeedMaPS, understanding YOLOv5's architecture and training process is crucial for exploring ways to enriching the dataset while maintaining accuracy.

2.3.2.1 Architecture

A paper was not published for YOLOv5, instead Ultralytics describes the model in detail in their official documentation at docs.ultralytics.com/yolov5/.

YOLOv5, like the other YOLO's, follows a single-stage detection approach, dividing its architecture into three key components[24]:

- **Backbone:** the backbone is responsible for extracting features from the input images. YOLOv5 uses the *New CSP-Darknet53* structure, which is a modification of the Darknet architecture that was used in previous versions of YOLO. This helps in reducing computational bottlenecks while maintaining accuracy.
- **Neck:** the neck connects the backbone and the head, and is used for aggregating features from different scales. YOLOv5 employs SPPF (Spatial Pyramid Pooling Fast) and New CSP-PAN structures, which combine features from different layers to improve the model's ability to detect objects at various sizes.
- **Head:** the head of the network is responsible for the final detection and classification of objects. YOLOv5 uses anchor boxes and predicts the class probabilities and bounding box coordinates for each anchor box. YOLOv5 uses the *YOLOv3 Head* to generate this final output.

2.3.2.2 Learning: Loss Functions

YOLOv5 is trained using a combination of three losses. Loss functions describe how well a model is performing in terms of a "cost" or an "error" for a given tuning of the model parameters. By examining the loss, the influence of each parameter is computed and updated with the purpose of reducing this cost. The loss in YOLOv5 is a combination of three individual loss functions:

1. Classes Loss (Binary Cross-Entropy Loss)
2. Objectness Loss (Binary Cross-Entropy Loss)
3. Location Loss (Complete Intersection over Union Loss)

Classes Loss (Binary Cross-Entropy Loss) measures the error of the classification task, which is a measure of how accurate the model is in predicting the correct class for each detected object. This loss is computed using Binary Cross-Entropy loss, which is a regular practice for multi-label classification problems.

Binary Cross-Entropy is Cross-Entropy, also called log-loss[25], used as a loss function for binary classification tasks. It is a measure of the difference between the predicted probabilities and the actual binary labels for a set of predictions. It penalizes predictions that are far from the actual labels, which helps the model to output probabilities closer to the actual binary labels. Binary cross-entropy loss is computed as shown below in Equation 2.1:

$$BCE = \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} -y^{(i)} \cdot \log(y^{(i)}) - (1 - \hat{y}^i) \log(1 - \hat{y}^i) \right) \quad (2.1)$$

Where:

- n is the number of samples
- $y^{(i)}$ is the true label for the i -th sample (0 or 1)
- $\hat{y}^{(i)}$ is the predicted probability of the positive class for the i -th sample

The Classes Loss is denoted as: L_{cls} , where $L_{cls} = BCE$.

Objectness Loss (Binary Cross-Entropy Loss) computes the error of detecting whether an object is present in a specific grid cell or not, which helps the model learn to differentiate between background and regions containing objects. This loss is also computed as with Binary Cross-Entropy. Objectness Loss is denoted as: L_{obj} , where $L_{obj} = BCE$.

Location Loss (Complete Intersection over Union Loss) measures the cost of localizing an object within a grid cell. It uses Complete Intersection over Union (CIoU) loss, which not only considers the overlapped area between the predicted boxes and ground truth boxes, but also accounts for the distance between their centers and their aspect ratio. This loss function improves the accuracy of bounding box regression by extending regular Intersection over Union (IoU) with additional geometric factors. Traditional IoU measures the overlap between the predicted bounding box and the ground truth bounding box, computed as shown in Equation 2.2:

$$IoU = \frac{\text{Area of Overlap}}{\text{Area of Union}} \quad (2.2)$$

Complete IoU (CIoU) extends IoU by adding two additional terms: a distance term and an aspect ratio term. The distance term penalizes the distance between the center points of the predicted and ground truth boxes, which encourages the model to place predicted boxes closer to the ground truth boxes. The aspect ratio term penalizes the difference in aspect ratios between the predicted boxes and ground truth boxes, which ensures a similar shape between the boxes. Equation 2.3 shows how the CIoU loss is computed[26]:

$$L_{CIoU} = 1 - IoU + \frac{\rho^2(b, b^{gt})}{c^2} + \alpha \cdot v \quad (2.3)$$

Where:

- $\frac{\rho^2(b, b^{gt})}{c^2}$ is the distance term
 - b and b^{gt} are the center points of the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes
 - $\rho^2(b, b^{gt})$ is the euclidian distance between these center points
 - c is the diagonal length of the smallest bounding box that covers both boxes
- $\alpha \cdot v$ is the aspect ratio term

- α is a positive trade-off parameter, defined as $\alpha = \frac{v}{(1-IoU)} + v$
- v measures the consistency of aspect ratio $v = \frac{4}{\pi^2} (\arctan \frac{w^{gt}}{h^{gt}} - \arctan \frac{w}{h})^2$

In YOLOv5 terms, Location Loss is denoted: L_{loc} , defined as $L_{loc} = L_{CIoU}$.

The Overall Loss ($J(w)$) for YOLOv5 combines these three losses as the sum of each multiplied by a corresponding weight, λ_i . Equation 2.4 below depicts the total loss function, $J(w)$, for YOLOv5:

$$J(w)_{YOLOv5} = \lambda_1 \cdot L_{cls} + \lambda_2 \cdot L_{obj} + \lambda_3 \cdot L_{loc} \quad (2.4)$$

2.3.2.3 Training Process

Training a YOLOv5 model for weed and crop recognition involves feeding it a large dataset of annotated images, where each plant object is labeled with a bounding box and a class. Throughout training, the model learns to map image features to object locations and classes by iteratively adjusting the model parameters to minimize the loss functions (minimize the difference between predicted and actual annotations) via backpropagation. Simply described, backpropagation in YOLOv5 works as follows[24]:

1. **Forward Pass:** during the forward pass, an input image is passed through the network, and predictions are generated. These predictions include bounding box coordinates, objectness scores, and class probabilities
2. **Loss Computation:** the predictions are compared to the ground truth labels using the loss function, $J(w)$
3. **Gradient Calculation:** the gradients of the loss function are computed with respect to **each** parameter in the network. This gradient is a vector, $\nabla J(w)$, representing how much each parameter contributed to the error (loss), computed using the chain-rule $\frac{\partial J}{\partial w_i}$ with respect to all parameters in the network
4. **Parameter Update:** the model parameters are updated using an optimization algorithm, typically Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) or one its variants (e.g. Adam). The gradient vector points in the direction of the maximum increase of the loss function, therefore, parameters are adjusted in the opposite direction of the gradient to reduce the loss

Common hyper-parameters are used when specifying the training process for deep learning model's:

- **Epochs:** the number of times the entire training dataset is passed through the model

- **Batch Size:** the number of images processed in a single training iteration
- **Learning Rate:** the step size, α , taken during parameter updates
- **Data Augmentation:** techniques applied to the training data to increase its diversity reduce overfitting

YOLOv5 uses some specific training strategies to enhance the model's performance and stability even further[24]. These strategies, along with the specific YOLOv5 data augmentation techniques, described in section 2.3.5, contribute to its overall efficiency and accuracy. Some key training strategies used are briefly described below:

- **Multi-scale training:** input images are randomly re-scaled during training to improve the model's ability to detect objects at various sizes
- **AutoAnchor:** anchor boxes are automatically optimized during training to better match the dataset's object characteristics
- **Warmup and Cosine LR Scheduler:** a learning rate scheduler adjusts the learning rate throughout training to improve convergence as learning becomes harder and preventing overfitting
- **Exponential Moving Average (EMA):** EMA weights are used to stabilize training, which improves generalization

2.3.2.4 Importance of Annotated Datasets

High-quality annotated datasets are **essential** for training YOLOv5 effectively. Accurate bounding boxes and class labels ensure that the model learns to correctly identify and localize plants, as opposed to inaccurate or inconsistent annotations that can negatively impact model performance. Since the dataset acts as ground truth, it is crucial that it contains correct annotations, as the model would otherwise be misled and penalized in the loss function, making it unable to learn detailed feature representations.

2.3.3 Evaluating Models

Being able to assess how a trained model performs is necessary in quantifying the model's effectiveness, both in classification tasks and object detection. Below are some important definitions that are needed to present the evaluation metrics:

- **True Positives (TP):** the number of correctly detected objects
- **False Positives (FP):** the number of incorrectly detected objects
- **False Negatives (FN):** the number of objects missed by the detector

The commonly evaluation metrics for classification and object detection tasks are presented below.

Precision (P) measures the proportion of correctly identified positive detections out of all positive predictions, which answers the question: "out of all the plants the model identified, how many were actually plants?". Precision is calculated as equation 2.5.

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2.5)$$

Recall (R) measures the proportion of actual positive instances correctly identified. It answers the question: "out of all the actual plants in the images, how many did the model find?". Recall is computed as equation 2.6:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2.6)$$

F1 Score ($F1$) is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, which provides a balanced measure of the overall accuracy. The F1 score is an instance of F score, where precision and recall is given equal importance. A F1 score of 1.0 (highest possible value) indicates perfect precision and recall, while a score of 0.0 (lowest possible value) indicates that precision and recall are zero. F1 score is computed as shown in equation 2.7:

$$F1 = \frac{2 * (P * R)}{P + R} \quad (2.7)$$

Mean Average Precision (mAP) is a widely used metric in object detection in general that considers both bounding box localization accuracy and classification confidence by averaging the Average Precision (AP) across all classes. It is especially useful, as it provides a more comprehensive assessment of the model's ability to detect and classify objects across different confidence thresholds. mAP is typically calculated at different IoU (Intersection over Union) thresholds, with the common benchmarks used for YOLOv5 being:

- $mAP@0.5$ (mAP50): predicted bounding boxes needs to have *atleast* 50% overlap with the ground truth boxes (as IoU) to be considered correct detections
- $mAP@0.5 : 0.95$ (mAP50-95): computes the performance across a range of IoU thresholds (e.g. 0.5, 0.55, 0.6, ..., 0.95)

Comparing the two different mAP thresholds, $mAP50$ is less strict than $mAP95$, and is usually used because it provides a good balance between precision and recall (as well as being relatively easy to compute). $mAP95$ is more comprehensive, as it evaluates the model's performance across a range of IoU thresholds, which

produce a more thorough assessment of the model’s ability to detect objects with high localization accuracy.

The general formula for computing mAP is listed below in equation 2.8:

$$mAP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^{k=n} AP_k \quad (2.8)$$

Where:

- n is the number of classes
- AP_k is the Average Precision for the k 'th class

These evaluation metrics are essential in understanding, as these provide the tools for assessing the impact of modifications between hypothesized changes and the current model. In short, the metrics described above helps evaluate the model’s performance as:

- Correctly identify crops and weeds (precision)
- Detect all instances of crops and weeds (recall)
- Achieve a balance between precision and recall (F1 score)
- Perform consistently across different confidence levels (mAP)

2.3.4 Data Augmentation and Synthetic Image Generation

The success of deep learning models, especially CNNs, is heavily dependent on the availability of large and diverse training datasets. Complex models, like YOLOv5, need large amounts of data to learn features that are both robust and enable good generalization abilities. However, gathering real-world data and labeling extensive datasets (especially manually) is expensive and time-consuming. In the context of weed/crop recognition, impractical attributes of real-world data are present as variations in field conditions, growth stages, and weed/crop species distributions. Tackling these impracticality’s are essential for teaching a deep learning model to distinguish between different weeds and crops in different fields, seasons, growth stages, weather conditions. This is where data augmentation provides value.

Data augmentation artificially expands the size and variety of a dataset by applying different transformations to the existing data. This technique is vital in computer vision in general, as it helps models handle variations in scale, viewpoint, illumination, and background. Exposing the model to variations in these during training helps prevent overfitting (where the model memorizes the training data instead of learning to generalize), which improves performance on unseen data (ability to generalize).

Figure 2.3: Illustration of geometric transformations

2.3.4.1 Data Augmentation Techniques

The commonly used data augmentation techniques in computer vision tasks can be broadly classified into two categories: geometric transformations and color manipulations.

Geometric transformations involve changing the spatial arrangement of pixels in an image, which is typically done as:

- **Rotation:** rotating the image by a specific degree
- **Scaling:** resizing the image to simulate objects appearing larger or smaller
- **Translation:** shifting the image horizontally or vertically to alter its position
- **Shearing:** skewing the image to simulate a change in the angle of the viewing plane
- **Flipping:** mirroring the image horizontally or vertically

These geometric transformations synthetically augment the dataset to have a broader representation, which can significantly enhance the performance of CNNs. Especially shearing and horizontal flipping has been found to increase performance for tasks such as hand gesture recognition[27].

Color manipulations involves modifying the image's color channels. This is typically done through adjusting:

Figure 2.4: Illustration of color manipulated augmentations

- **Brightness:** making the image brighter or darker
- **Contrast:** changes the difference between light and dark areas in the image
- **Saturation:** changing the intensity of colors

2.3.5 YOLOv5 Specific Augmentations

YOLOv5 employs a mix of standard and specialized data augmentation techniques to boost its robustness and ability to generalize. Beyond the geometric and color manipulations already mentioned, YOLOv5 uses unique strategies to further diversify the training data[24]:

- **Mosaic Augmentation:** this involves combining four training images into one, which helps the model manage objects at various scales, translations, and occlusions more effectively (illustrated in figure 2.5)
- **Copy-Paste Augmentation:** this method involves copying random patches from one image and pasting them onto another, creating new training samples with novel object combinations and backgrounds
- **MixUp Augmentation:** this involves blending two training images and their labels, generating composite images that enhance the models ability to handle uncertainty and preventing overfitting

2.4 Related Work

The growing need for sustainable and efficient agricultural practices has driven substantial research in automating weed management through computer vision and deep learning techniques, which will be the main theme in related works examined. This section reviews studies related to the research questions that guides this thesis, focusing on the existing approaches related to the core challenges:

(a) Example 1

(b) Example 2

Figure 2.5: Illustration of Mosaic augmentation

1. RQ1: hierarchical classification for specific weed recognition (especially how to re-label "Monocot" and "Dicot" more specifically)
2. RQ2: leveraging data from partially annotated images (utilizing I-GIS approved annotations from unapproved images in training)

2.4.1 Hierarchical Classification and Label Refinement

One of the main challenges in weed detection is progressing beyond merely classifying broad categories (such as "Monocot" and "Dicot") to identify specific weed species. This detailed level of recognition is crucial for targeted weed control and identifying emerging weeds in fields, conserving pesticide usage and choosing the effective treatment for fields.

Cerri et al. (2014) presented a hierarchical multi-label classification (HMC) approach using local neural networks[28]. The HMC-LMLP (Hierarchical Multi-label Classification with Local Multi-Layer Perceptron) method employs a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) network for each hierarchical level, where predictions at one level serve as inputs for the next. This approach leverages the hierarchical structure of data to improve classification performance, providing a valuable framework for refining broad categories like Monocot and Dicot into specific weed classes. The method's ability to capture dependencies between classes through incremental training with individual classifiers that focus on subsets is particularly interesting and could be a viable consideration in exploring how to tackle RQ1.

Skovsen et al. (2019) introduced the GrassClover Image Dataset[29], emphasizing hierarchical labeling and semantic segmentation to understand species in agriculture. This work highlights the importance of hierarchical annotations for

training robust models and includes methods for generating synthetic images with pixel-wise hierarchical labels. While the primary focus differs from RQ1, the paper’s approach to hierarchical species understanding aligns well with RQ1. The methods for hierarchical labeling and species identification within images could provide a useful way of refining labels.

Additionally, the paper describes creating synthetic images with hierarchical labels and integrating them with real-world, unlabeled images, which is particularly relevant to RQ2. This could possibly assist in addressing RQ2 by augmenting I-GIS training data with synthetic data derived from approved thumbnails in partially annotated images.

A study by Lee et al. (2017) examined how deep learning models, specifically CNNs, learn hierarchical features from leaf images for plant classification[30]. They found that venation patterns were critical for leaf classification and that CNNs could learn features aligning with botanical hierarchies. This method aligns with RQ1 in refining broad categories into specific weed classes using hierarchical classification. The paper’s insights into how CNNs can extract meaningful features from raw data provide a valuable foundation for the hierarchical classification approach used in conjunction with CropDiva.

Additionally, the methodology for feature learning and visualization is relevant to RQ2, which focuses on leveraging data from partially annotated images. The paper’s emphasis on learning features from raw representations and understanding the internal workings of CNNs can assist in developing methods to utilize approved annotations from unapproved images. This approach also supports the augmentation of training data with synthetic images derived from approved thumbnails, which addresses the challenges of unknown and low-quality weed classes within the broader categories.

2.4.2 Weed Detection Techniques

Deep learning techniques have shown superior performance over traditional machine learning approaches in weed detection tasks, especially in feature extraction and classification accuracy[4]. Newer studies have explored various deep learning architectures, including YOLO (You Only Look Once), for real-time weed detection in agriculture settings.

Haq et al. (2023) evaluated different versions of YOLO models for weed detection in wheat crops and found that YOLOv5 offered a good balance of speed and accuracy, highlighting its suitability for real-time applications in agricultural fields[13]. Their focus on inference time and detection accuracy, particularly in real-time applications, emphasizes the need for efficient and accurate models for practical weed management. This aligns with the overall goals of thesis, which aims to improve the performance of I-GIS’s YOLOv5 model while utilizing the annotated data more efficiently.

Hasan et al. (2024) developed an object-level benchmark dataset for corn crops and evaluated YOLOv7, YOLOv8, and Faster-RCNN models[14]. They

highlighted the strong performance of YOLOv7 and YOLOv8 in achieving high mAP, while maintaining suitable inference speeds for real-time applications. Generally, the paper showcases the suitability of YOLOv8 for achieving high accuracy while maintaining acceptable inference speeds in agricultural tasks. While object detection models like YOLO excel at locating and classifying weeds, their accuracy can be further enhanced by incorporating instance segmentation techniques. Sampurno et al. (2024) successfully implemented YOLOv8 for instance segmentation of uncut weeds, tree trunks, and poles in orchard plantations[31]. Their work demonstrates the potential of extending YOLO models beyond bounding box detection to achieve pixel-level accuracy in weed segmentation, which is relevant for tasks that require precise weed localization, e.g. robotic weeding or targeted herbicide application.

2.4.3 Data Augmentation and Synthetic Data

Data augmentation is crucial for tasks like weed detection where diverse training data is essential for robust performance, making it important to explore the relevant techniques for generating synthetic images and augmenting existing datasets in agricultural contexts.

One approach to address limited training data is to create synthetic images. Sapkota et al. (2022) demonstrated the effectiveness of using synthetic images for weed detection and biomass estimation in cotton fields[32]. Their study incorporated two types of synthetic instances: real plant instances extracted from UAV images and artificial instances generated using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). Notably, they found that models trained on real plant instance-based synthetic images outperformed those trained on GAN-generated instances, which suggests that the quality of synthetic data significantly impacts the model's performance. This underlines how important a careful evaluation of the quality and realism of synthetic images is when using them for data augmentation.

Another relevant approach is explored by Hasan et al. (2023), who utilized image patches to improve crop and weed recognition[33]. They first enhanced images using GANs, then divided them into overlapping patches. Informative patches were selected using features like the variance of the Laplacian and the mean frequency of Fast Fourier Transforms. This strategy, evaluated on various datasets, demonstrated significant improvements in classification accuracy, particularly by addressing intra-class dissimilarity and inter-class similarity. This highlights the potential of utilizing image patches and selective augmentation techniques to enhance the representation of specific weed classes within a broader dataset.

As discussed in section 2.4.1, Skovsen et al. (2019) further emphasized the utility of synthetic images in their study on semantic and hierarchical species understanding in agriculture, where they integrated synthetic images with real-world, unlabeled images, and demonstrated the potential of combining different data sources to improve model training[29].

2.4.4 Learning from Partially Annotated Data

Scenarios where a significant portion of the data remains partially annotated, as the case of the RoboWeedMaPS dataset, is not optimal as this is unused. Therefore, exploring ways to address this challenge is essential as it could better the model's performance and generalization capabilities.

Li et al. (2024) tackles a similar issue by evaluating semi-supervised learning frameworks for multi-class weed detection. Their work demonstrates the effectiveness of teacher-student models and pseudo-labeling techniques in leveraging unlabeled data to achieve performance comparable to fully supervised approaches, even with significantly less labeled data[3]. This study in particular highlights the potential of semi-supervised learning techniques in reducing the reliance on extensive labeled datasets and instead utilizing partially annotated data effectively, which is relevant to RQ2.

Furthermore, identifying and correcting mislabeled instances within partially annotated data is crucial for ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the training dataset. Müller and Markert (2019) present a non-parametric pipeline for identifying mislabeled instances across various data types, including images[34]. Their work shows the importance of data quality, and they provide a practical tool for improving the integrity of training datasets, especially when dealing with partially annotated data. Similarly, Pleiss et al. (2020) introduce the Area Under the Margin (AUM) statistic as a method for detecting mislabeled samples[35]. By leveraging this AUM ranking, mislabeled instances can be effectively identified and removed, leading to improved model performance, which is relevant in generally bettering the dataset and thereby model's abilities.

These studies all highlight the potential of utilizing partially annotated data through semi-supervised learning and mislabeling detection techniques. This approach aligns with the goal of maximizing the utilization of existing annotated data, as is the case with the I-GIS dataset, where a large portion of the data is partially annotated. While these techniques primarily focus on classification tasks, adapting them for object detection, particularly in the context of the YOLOv5 model, requires further exploration.

2.4.5 Positioning the Research Questions in the Current Literature

This examination of related work reveals that while significant progress has been made in applying deep learning to weed recognition, there are no direct solutions to the specific challenges this thesis sets out to explore. Therefore, there is a gap in the current research to focus specifically on:

- Robust hierarchical classification methods that address inter- and intra-class similarities and handle varying degrees of annotation
- Efficient techniques for leveraging data from partially annotated images, which can mitigate the limitations of relying on fully approved data

2.5 Key findings and Addressing Research Goals

2.5.1 Key Findings

The reviewed literature showed the significant progress made in applying deep learning to weed (and crop) recognition, particularly through models like CNNs and YOLO variations. The examined studies generally demonstrated the effectiveness of these models in achieving high accuracy in weed detection and classification tasks, specifically for some crop types and under controlled conditions. Several key findings came out of this analysis:

- **Hierarchical Classification:** the importance of hierarchical classification for detailed weed recognition is noted, especially for tasks requiring specific weed species identification (Skovsen et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2017; Cerri et al., 2014). However, existing methods often focus on specific crop types or lack the flexibility to handle varying levels of annotation detail.
- **Data Augmentation and Synthetic Data:** the use of data augmentation and synthetic data is crucial for enhancing model performance, especially when dealing with limited labeled data (Skovsen et al., 2019; Sapkota et al., 2022; Hasan et al., 2023). Studies demonstrate the effectiveness of techniques like GANs, image patches, and synthetic instances derived from real data in improving model's accuracy.
- **Real-time Detection:** emphasizes the need for efficient and accurate models for real-time weed detection, especially for practical applications in agricultural fields (Haq et al., 2023; Hasan et al., 2024). YOLO models (known for their speed and accuracy) are increasingly utilized for such tasks, demonstrating their suitability for real-time applications.
- **Leveraging Partially Annotated Data:** the challenge of utilizing partially annotated data, where a significant portion of images contains unapproved annotations is investigated. These studies demonstrated that semi-supervised learning and mislabeling detection techniques can effectively leverage unlabeled or partially labeled data to achieve comparable performance to fully supervised approaches, even with significantly less labeled data. These findings presents insights into maximizing data utilization while also reducing the reliance on manual annotation.

Despite these advancements, no directly applicable solutions were identified for the proposed research questions:

- **Robust Hierarchical Classification:** existing methods often struggle to handle the complexity of real-world agricultural datasets with diverse weed species and annotation levels, and no examined proposed solutions proposes a direct solution to the research question, RQ1.

- **Efficient Utilization of Partially Annotated Data:** the current techniques for leveraging partially annotated data are primarily focused on classification tasks, making them not directly applicable to I-GIS dataset and YOLOv5 model.
- **Scalability and Generalizability to I-GIS Dataset:** many studies rely on relatively small datasets, or specific crop types and environmental conditions, potentially limiting the generalizability of their findings to I-GIS dataset.

2.5.2 Addressing the Research Goals

To address the challenge of refining the broad "Monocot" and "Dicot" labels into more specific weed classes (RQ1), this thesis proposes a hierarchical classification approach leveraging the existing CropDiva classification framework. The proposed solution involves training a CropDiva model on a subset of the RoboWeedMaPS dataset, with images from the same field. This subset should specifically exclude the "Dicot" class. The trained CropDiva model can then be used to predict the classes of unapproved thumbnails, particularly those belonging to the "Dicot" category. By setting a threshold for confident classification of the model predictions based on test-set evaluation, this approach will allow for an automated re-labeling of the "Dicot" class into more specific categories for predictions above the threshold. This process effectively increases the representation of specific weed classes within the dataset without requiring manual revisiting of each image, which promotes a more balanced dataset.

The unique challenge of utilizing partially annotated images in the RoboWeedMaPS dataset, where some plant instances are labeled while others remain unannotated within the same image, demands a tailored solution. While semi-supervised learning techniques, such as those explored by Li et al. (2024), shows promise in leveraging unlabeled data for object detection tasks like this, their work primarily address scenarios with fully labeled or fully unlabeled images, rendering their pseudo-labeling approach unsure in regards to this task of partially annotated images.

To overcome this limitation, this thesis introduces a novel **Thumbnail Injection Framework**. Instead of relying on pseudo-labeling for entire images, this framework directly incorporates the data present in the existing approved thumbnails from partially annotated images. Inspired by the success of synthetic data generation methods in related works (such as Sapkota et al., 2022 and Hasan et al., 2023), the Thumbnail Injection Framework should systematically extract and inject these approved thumbnails into fully approved images, resulting in fully approved images with thumbnails from unapproved images. This process should ensure realistic placement and avoid issues like overlapping and occlusion. This approach is strengthened by the specific YOLOv5 augmentation techniques that combines (mosaic) or mixes different images (MixUp), suggesting that inserting images with hard borders, like a cutout plant instance thumbnail,

performs equally to the plant originally being in the image. However, this would require realistic placement of thumbnails and no overlapping.

This framework is hypothesized to enhance the diversity and richness of the training data, which ultimately aims to improve the model's performance and ability to generalize. The Thumbnail Injector Framework aims to maximize the amount of existing approved annotations, promoting a more efficient and effective training process for the CropWeed YOLOv5 model.

Therefore, the interesting direction to explore in regards to RQ2 can be further specified as: can a robust and context-aware thumbnail injector framework be designed and implemented to augment the approved images with thumbnails from partially approved images? The framework should ensure realistic and consistent integration of thumbnails while avoiding issues like overlapping and occlusion.

Chapter 3

System Design and Methodology

This chapter presents two approaches to address the class imbalance and data under-utilization in the I-GIS RoboWeedMaPS dataset, utilizing the CropDiva model framework for hierarchical classification and a novel Thumbnail Injection Framework for data augmentation, aiming to improve the performance of I-GIS the YOLOv5 object detection model, CropWeed.

All relevant code from the project is collected and available at the GitHub repository: https://github.com/heltechael/injector_tool.

3.1 Dataset and Preprocessing

3.1.1 I-GIS Dataset Overview

The I-GIS dataset, which can be accessed through RoboWeedMaPS, consists of a vast collection of images captured from real farming operations across Denmark. These images are primarily acquired through the use of a specialized camera system mounted on an autonomous robot or an ATV. The images are from diverse fields containing various crops, weeds, and other elements found in the fields. The dataset is used to train the YOLOv5 model, CropWeed, which in turn is used to analyze and generate spray-maps for farmers.

A key characteristic of I-GIS RoboWeedMaPS dataset is the distinction between images "Marked for Training" and those not "Marked for Training". This distinction is crucial because the YOLOv5 model is *exclusively* trained on images "Marked for Training" and all annotations within these images are implicitly considered approved. This means that a significant portion of the dataset, while containing approved annotations, is not directly used in training the YOLOv5 model. Images in the dataset can be split into two categories:

- **Images marked for training:** these images are the training set for the YOLOv5 model. Each image contains multiple bounding box annotations, each representing an individual plant instance. Every annotation within these images is associated with an EPPO code, identifying the specific plant type
- **Images *not* marked for training:** this subset of the dataset consists of images that are not used in training the YOLOv5 model. However, these images may contain a considerable amount of approved annotations (thumbnails) that are currently not utilized

For an image to be "Marked for Training", either all annotations in the image are flagged as *Approved* or the remaining *Unapproved* annotations are implicitly

Figure 3.1: Examples of raw images from RoboWeedMaPS

Metric	Approved Images	Not Approved Images
Number of Images	59,796	70,442
Approved Annotations	605,913	332,295
Unapproved Annotations	1,859,845	-
Total Annotations	2,465,758	-

Table 3.1: Overview of I-GIS Dataset

approved by either Rasmus Nyholm Jørgensen (AU) or Laura-Carlota Paz (I-GIS).

Since images are taken with different cameras and configurations, they have varying resolutions, aspect ratios, and area imaged. Examples of the raw images are shown in figure 3.1.

3.1.2 Dataset Statistics

Table 3.1 provides an overview of the I-GIS dataset and highlights the differences between images "Marked for Training" and those that are not.

3.1.3 Classes Used in Training

12 classes are included when training the YOLOv5 model, which has been manually annotated by experts. The included classes are: Monocot (PPPM), Dicot (PPPDD), Faba bean (VICFX), Field Pea (PIBSA), Maize (ZEAMX), Potato (SOLTU), Spinach (SPQOL), Sugar beet (BEAVA), Creeping Thistle (CIRAR), White cabbage (BRSOL), Buckwheat (FAGES), and Lupinus (1LUPG).

An additional label, Plant Stem Emergence Zone (PSEZ), is also included as a training class. However, this is not a real plant EPPO code, but is instead used in conjunction with instances of Maize (ZEAMX), Sugar beet (BEAVA), and White cabbage (BRSOL).

Class	Approved	Not Approved	Total
PPPM	11905	369527	381432
PPPDD	67848	1293166	1361014
VICFX	17444	3106	20550
PIBSA	10654	0	10654
ZEAMX	15404	7139	22543
SOLTU	4917	516	5433
SPQOL	5189	12305	17494
BEAVA	21101	3462	24563
CIRAR	18666	1023	19689
BRSOL	26562	3834	30396
FAGES	11148	11044	22192
1LUPG	1971	972	2943
PSEZ	16406	44238	60644

Table 3.2: Table of class instances used in training

3.1.4 Class Distribution in Images Marked for Training

Table 3.2 presents the distribution of approved and not approved annotations within the images "Marked for Training." It is essential to note that the YOLOv5 training process treats all annotations within these images as implicitly approved, so the "Not Approved" column is provided for informational purposes.

3.1.5 Approved Annotations in Images Not Marked for Training

As seen in table 3.1, there are 332,295 approved annotations in the images not currently used for training the model. The distribution of approved annotations for the classes used in the model are shown below, excluding Monocot and Dicot, as these classes are not interesting for injection, since the purpose is to better the models ability to generalize to more specific classes of interest:

- VICFX (Faba bean): 10,997
- PIBSA (Field Pea): 1,204
- ZEAMX (Maize): 4,697
- SOLTU (Potato): 1,519
- SPQOL (Spinach): 15,251
- BEAVA (Sugar beet): 4,603
- CIRAR (Creeping Thistle): 18,644
- BRSOL (White cabbage): 64

- FAGES (Buckwheat): 59,727
- 1LUPG (Lupinus): 6,703

3.1.6 Challenges

There are two significant challenges of I-GIS dataset for training the YOLOv5 model:

- **Class Imbalance:** as evident from the total distribution of class instances used in training (figure 3.2), the dataset has a severe class imbalance. The Monocot (PPPM) and Dicot (PPDD) classes are heavily dominant, representing an overwhelming part of the annotations. This imbalance can lead to a model bias, where the YOLOv5 model becomes adept at recognizing Monocot or Dicot, but in turn struggles to (accurately) identify the specific weed species that are less represented
- **Data Under-Utilization:** a considerable number of images within the I-GIS dataset contain at least one approved annotation within the image, however, they are *not* used in training. This results in a great amount of potentially valuable annotated data being left unused as seen in table 3.1

Figure 3.2: Total distribution of class instances used in training

3.2 Addressing Class Imbalance and Data Under-Utilization

As presented in section 3.1, I-GIS dataset presents two key challenges that could hinder the performance of the YOLOv5 model: a significant class imbalance, with "Monocot" and "Dicot" classes dominating the data, and the under-utilization of "Approved" annotated data not used in training. This thesis investigates two approaches to address these challenges.

3.2.1 Hierarchical Classification with CropDiva

To mitigate the problem of class imbalance, this thesis explores a hierarchical classification approach using the CropDiva model. CropDiva is a plant classification model developed by the research group, Computer Vision in Biosystems, at Aarhus University, and is trained on a curated subset of the I-GIS dataset from that specifically excludes the "Dicot" class.

By training on this subset, CropDiva learns to distinguish between a variety of specific weed species without being biased towards the overly general PPPDD (Dicot) label. Once trained, CropDiva is used to predict labels for thumbnails currently classified as PPPDD (Dicot). If the model predicts a specific weed class with a confidence score above a pre-determined threshold, the thumbnail is re-labeled from PPPDD (Dicot) to that specific class.

This re-labeling process, controlled by CropDiva's predictions, will effectively re-label instances from the dominant "Dicot" category into more specific weed classes. This has the potential to improve the balance of the RoboWeedMaPS dataset, which in turn would improve the YOLOv5 model (CropWeed) by potentially improving its ability to recognize and differentiate between the less-represented weed species.

3.2.2 Levering Under-utilized Approved Data with Thumbnail Injection Framework

To tackle the data under-utilization issue, this thesis introduces a Thumbnail Injection Framework. The primary purpose of this framework is to utilize the approved thumbnails from the non-approved images into the training data for CropWeed. The framework achieves this by strategically injecting these unused thumbnails into fully approved images, augmenting the existing training data with the large amount of un-utilized instances (distribution showed in figure 3.3) that would otherwise not be used.

The framework involves several key steps: loading images, thumbnails, and annotations, finding suitable locations within approved images that ensures no overlap with existing annotations, inserting the thumbnails, and updating and outputting the annotation data to reflect these newly "injected images".

3.3 Data Structure and Access in RoboWeedMaPS

RoboWeedMaPS stores the data in a relational database. The database consists of multiple tables, with the relevant tables for fetching image-annotations being "Images", "Annotations", and "AnnotationData". The "Images" table contains information about each image, including its filename (FileName), associated field upload identifier (UploadId), and whether it's marked for training (UseForTraining). The "Annotations" table links images to their annotation data stored in the "AnnotationsData" table. The table stores the bounding box annotations for each plant instance within an image, plant

Distribution of Approved Class Instances From Non-approved Images

Figure 3.3: Distribution of approved annotations from unapproved images of classes used in training, excluding Monocot and Dicot

identification code (PlantId), bounding box coordinates (MinX, MaxX, MinY, MaxY), and whether the annotation is approved (Approved) and an associated score (ClassificationScore). There is additional annotation data, such as partly annotated GrowthStage data, but it is not relevant to this thesis. All data for this thesis were directly acquired from I-GIS local NAS-server and the RoboWeedMaPS database, providing access to both the raw image data (stored as ".jpg" files) and the complete set of annotations.

3.3.1 Image Storage: NAS-Server

I-GIS has two PC's:

- *Dev*: developer machine
- *Prod*: production machine

Images are stored on a NAS-server mounted on the *Dev* machine. Image files are stored in folders named after their corresponding RoboWeedMaPS *UploadId*'s. Interacting with the image data involves giving the *Dev* machine a command to copy an image. The NAS-server then accesses the image and copies it over the network to the *Dev* machine.

3.3.2 Handling Large Image Data

Working with **real data** of this volume requires careful consideration and optimization to reduce downtime as much as possible when handling the images. Processes such as copying images and extracting thumbnails need to be optimized to handle the volume effectively. A key way to reduce processing times significantly, such as reducing the time to copy 5000 images from over 24 hours to just 3-4 hours, is using **parallel processing** and **batch processing**.

3.3.2.1 Utilizing Multiprocessing and Batch Processing

Parallel processing involves using multiple worker processes that run at the same time. Each one tackles a portion of the workload, so multiple images are processed simultaneously. This way of distributing tasks ensures that processing is balanced and efficient, making full use of the system's CPU cores and avoiding any idle time (e.g. waiting for the NAS-server to transfer the image over the network).

Batch processing further optimizes this by grouping images into batches. These batches are then processed in parallel, which helps manage the data more efficiently and reduces the overhead of processing images one-by-one. This approach minimizes downtime and maximizes throughput.

Of course, having too many processes make requests to the NAS-server can saturate the network and overwhelm the NAS, slowing data transfers despite parallel execution. This could affect the workers at I-GIS, which is not highly undesirable. Therefore, a small delay of 1 second was agreed upon after every 25 images copied. Additionally, a balance between the number of processes and network saturation was chosen based on simple experiments of small image batches. A good balance was found to be 10 processes with a batch size of 25.

By using parallel processing and batching, the computation time required to extract 5,000 images was reduced from approximately 24 hours to approximately 4 hours.

3.3.2.2 Thumbnail Extraction

For both the CropDiva classification model and the Thumbnail Injection Framework, individual images of plant instances (thumbnails) were required for training and augmentation. These thumbnails were extracted from the RoboWeedMaPS database as annotations and I-GIS NAS server for image files.

A Python script, `extract_thumbnails.py`, was used to extract all annotated thumbnails from each image using the CSV annotation file with the possibility of blacklisting certain EPPO codes (e.g. "Monocot" or "Dicot" if desired). The script creates a specific output directory based on the current date and the approval status of annotations, meaning approved and unapproved annotations placed in corresponding directories. A function iterates through the CSV annotations, counting the total approved annotations for progress tracking. If the EPPO code

of an annotation is not blacklisted, it extracts the bounding box region from the image, creates a directory named after the EPPO code (if it does not exist already), and saves the thumbnail with a specified filename format (typically ".png"). The script uses **OpenCV** for image processing and **tqdm** for progress indication.

Thumbnails for use in CropDiva and the Injector can not be shared, since CropDiva relies on the same image dimensions (e.g. 224-by-224), while the injector should use the original scales. Therefore, a flag for adding *scaling and padding* is set by the user. If flagged, the output thumbnails are scaled and padded as follows:

1. *Scale up* the thumbnail if it smaller than a threshold of 50px
2. *Resize* the thumbnail to fit within the dimensions `DESIRED_DIM x DESIRED_DIM`, typically 224x224, while maintaining aspect ratio
3. *Pad* the resized thumbnail with black borders to fit the desired dimensions

This option of scaled and padded thumbnails are used for CropDiva. For the injector, thumbnails are cutout with the exact pixel-representation present in the original image. Figures 3.4 and 3.5 showcases examples of extracted thumbnails for the purpose of training CropDiva and injection, respectively.

3.4 CropDiva Classification Model

CropDiva is a framework for building and training plant classification models developed by Anders Krogh Mortensen and Rasmus Nyholm Jørgensen at the Computer Vision in Biosystems research group at Aarhus University. CropDiva was specifically designed to address the challenge of refining broad plant categories like "Monocot" and "Dicot" into more specific weed classes. This is crucial for introducing new classes to the YOLOv5 model in the future, as it ensures that instances of the new species are not mistakenly classified as belonging to the largely represented "Monocot" or "Dicot" classes.

3.4.1 Hierarchical Classification with CropDiva

Previous work by Anders and the research group has already achieved high-accuracy results in experimentation. However not published results, it has already shown the potential in classifying plant species of this problem structure with a high accuracy, making it very suited for use in this task. Additionally, using CropDiva saves a significant amount of time and resources compared to developing a new classification model from scratch, while also allowing for future exploration and incorporation of new models if desired. Scoping the thesis project to only focus on *one* novel new framework is essential given the natural time-constraints of a 5 month end-to-end thesis period.

Figure 3.4: Scaled and padded thumbnails used for training CropDiva

3.4.2 Model Training and Configuration

CropDiva provides a customizable and modular structure that allow users to experiment with various CNN architectures (e.g., ResNet, EfficientNet), pooling methods, loss functions, optimizers, and augmentation techniques. The CropDiva repository is publicly available at https://github.com/anderskm/CropDiva_classification/, with the branch `tfv2.13` being foundation for this work.

Following the recommended training-command in the repository description, this thesis adopted the configuration with minor changes, as this approach had shown to be effective for this task of plant classification. Additionally, the proposed configuration choices were intuitive, requiring no changes of model, loss function, or optimizer.

3.4.2.1 Model: EfficientNetV2S

An EfficientNetV2S architecture was used within the CropDiva framework for its balance of accuracy and computational efficiency (the original paper is conveniently titled "Smaller Models and Faster Training"[36]). The model was initialized with average pooling and pre-trained ImageNet weights to take advantage of the existing feature representations and thereby facilitating faster trainings.

3.4.2.2 Dataset Preparation

The training dataset consisted of a subset of the entire RoboWeedMaPS dataset, specifically only images from the field "F6" from Flakkebjerg. The RoboWeedMaPS UploadId's used was: 1372, 1373, 1378, 1379, 1380, 1381, 1384, 1385, 1386, 1387, 1394, and 1395. All annotated instances (thumbnails) were extracted from all images and separated as "Approved" and "Not Approved". Thumbnails are extracted as described in section 3.3.2.2, and figure 3.4 shows some examples of extracted thumbnails for the dataset used in CropDiva.

This subset of the original dataset consists of 81,319 approved thumbnails. However, only classes exceeding 500 samples are including in the training, ensuring sufficient sample sizes for the model to confidently learn feature

representations. The dataset for training consists of 80,556 samples and is comprised of the classes and their representation:

- 1CHEG: 12,028
- 1CRUF: 609
- 1LUPG: 8,149
- 1URTF: 605
- ATXPA: 501
- FAGES: 43,558
- POLAV: 1,964
- POLLA: 1,253
- PPPMM: 2,590
- VERPE: 2,528
- VICFX: 4,041
- VIOAR: 2,730

This excludes the dominant "Dicot" class as the purpose is to assess the instances of "Dicots" and re-label the instances to one of the other classes in the model. The dataset was split into training, validation, and test sets using a ratio of [0.70, 0.15, 0.15]. This is a standard practice, as the model uses the validation set to evaluate the performance during training, and the test set for final evaluation as completely unseen data. This evaluation on the test set is also crucial in computing thresholds for accurate re-labeling.

3.4.2.3 Training Parameters

The training parameters used in training were:

- A Focal (FocalCrossEntropy) loss function was used to address the class imbalance, as it down-weights the contribution of easy examples and focuses on harder-to-classify instances, making it an intuitive choice for this task
- The Adam optimizer was chosen as it enables efficient convergence during training due to its adaptive learning rate capabilities, as well as being a commonly used optimizer for classification tasks like this
- A learning rate of 0.0001 was used to optimize the model's weights as this performed sensibly during experimentation
- The model was trained for 200 epochs with a batch size of 32

- Random contrast adjustment with a factor of 0.2 and horizontal and vertical flipping were used for data augmentation, which were applied during training with the purpose of increasing the dataset's diversity, mimicking different field-conditions, thereby improving the models robustness and ability to generalize

3.4.3 Evaluation and Threshold Selection

The goal of using CropDiva is to **confidently** re-label "Dicot" thumbnails into more specific weed classes. To ensure that the suggested re-labels are highly reliable, determining an appropriate confidence threshold for accepting CropDiva's predictions is essential.

To determine an accepted confidence threshold, precision-recall curves were generated for each class based on CropDiva's predictions on the test set. For each class, two potential thresholds were computed:

- **Optimal Threshold:** the threshold where precision begins to drop below 1 (perfect precision) on the test set, which prioritizes extremely high-confidence predictions, aiming to minimize false positives
- **Median Threshold:** the median threshold value among those with perfect precision on the test set, which provides a more balanced approach, considering the distribution of confidence scores and potentially re-labeling a larger number of thumbnails

By inferring the model to predict the labels of all "Dicot" thumbnails, a list of the model's predicted labels and their associated confidence scores (computed using softmax) is generated. Utilizing the **optimal threshold**, which ensures perfect precision (1.0) based on the test set evaluation, prediction scores (confidence score) above this threshold can be **confidently** accepted. The corresponding thumbnails are then re-labeled with the model's predicted class.

3.4.3.1 Computing Thresholds

To effectively re-label unapproved thumbnails using a trained CropDiva model, it is important to determine precise confidence thresholds that ensures a very high reliability in the model's predictions, since this approach omits human assistance. To achieve this, a sufficient threshold of the models predictive confidence needs to be computed, which is achieved through the foundational work of Anders Krogh Mortensen's "`analyse_predictions.py`" script. This script calculates precision-recall curves and determines optimal thresholds for each class based on the model's predictions.

However, upon examining the CropDiva codebase[37], it was discovered that the model outputs raw logits or scores, which are not normalized probabilities. To address this and ensure the accurate computation of confidence thresholds, a revised version of the script, "`analyse_predictions_softmax.py`"[38] was developed.

This revised script applies a softmax function which converts the raw logits into a probability distribution over the classes. By applying softmax to the model's outputs, the predictions are transformed into normalized probabilities that sum up to 1 for each sample. The softmax function, $s(x_i)$, is defined as:

$$s(x_i) = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N e^{x_j}} \quad (3.1)$$

Where x_i is the raw logit for class i , and N is the total number of classes.

The revised script applies softmax to the model's predictions before calculating the precision-recall curves and determining the optimal thresholds. It also applies softmax to the predictions for each individual class before plotting the histograms and calculating the threshold statistics. This ensures that the confidence thresholds are computed based on valid probability values. The optimal thresholds are computed for each class as the following:

1. **Load predictions:** read the model's predictions for each sample
2. **Apply softmax:** apply the softmax function to the predictions, converting them into normalized probabilities
3. **Compute precision-recall curves:** calculate the PR-curves for each class using the softmax probabilities and the true labels of the test set
4. **Compute optimal threshold:** determine the optimal threshold for each class by finding the threshold value that maximizes the F1 score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall
5. **Store optimal thresholds:** store the optimal threshold for each class, along with other relevant statistics such as the precision, recall, and F1 score at the optimal threshold

These thresholds enable confident re-labeling of the unapproved thumbnails without human intervention, as they ensure that only predictions with a high degree of confidence are considered, which significantly minimizes the risk of misclassification and thus maintaining the integrity of the re-labeling process.

3.5 Thumbnail Injector Framework

The Thumbnail Injector Framework is designed to propose a way to utilize the unused approved thumbnails in the training of the YOLOv5 model, CropWeed. The primary purpose of this framework is to augment the dataset by injecting approved thumbnails from partially annotated (not approved) images into fully approved images. This allows the use of all approved annotations that would otherwise remain unused, which aims to enrich the training dataset without the need for additional manual annotation. The framework should be strategic in integrating these approved thumbnails to ensure realistic placement and avoids issues such as overlapping and occlusion.

3.5.1 Framework Design Principles

The framework is developed using the principles of Clean Code[39] by Robert C. Martin at best ability. The design goals of the framework is efficiency, maintainability, and scalability, therefore the Thumbnail Injector Framework is built upon the following core design principles to ensure these:

- **Modularity:** it is structured into individual modules (classes) responsible for specific tasks: data loading, thumbnail selection, space detection, injection, and annotation updates. This separation of concerns promotes code readability, maintainability, and making it easy to make changes in the future
- **Efficiency:** given the potential for processing a large number of images, the framework needs to emphasize computational efficiency. For example, instead of exhaustive pixel-by-pixel iteration for free space detection, a grid-based approach is employed, significantly reducing computational complexity
- **Scalability:** the framework is designed to scale efficiently with larger datasets. The modular architecture and data handling mechanisms ensure that processing time increases linearly with the number of images and thumbnails, avoiding exponential growth in computational demands
- **Data Integrity:** preserving the integrity of I-GIS original dataset is crucial. The framework therefore creates copies of images for injection, leaving the original data untouched
- **Configurability:** settings and parameters are configurable, which allows for fine-tuning the injection process based on specific dataset characteristics and desired augmentation levels

3.5.2 Input and Output

At a high level, the thumbnail injector takes thumbnails, images and an associated annotation file as inputs, and output injected images with the thumbnails clipped in along with an associated updated annotation file:

- **[IN] Images:** approved annotated images (fully approved images that are marked for training), including both the image data and their associated annotation files
- **[IN] Thumbnails:** approved thumbnails (annotated bounding boxes) from unapproved images
- **[OUT] Injected images:** input images with clipped-in thumbnails, including updated annotation files

Figure 3.5: Examples of thumbnails for injection with preserved scaling and sizing

- **[OUT]** Updated annotation CSV file: all annotation data for injected images

Thumbnails for injection are extracted as described in section 3.3.2.2, with figure 3.5 showing examples of thumbnails preserving their original size.

3.5.3 Injection Process

A flow diagram of the injection process is shown in figure 3.6. The framework's algorithm follows a systematic approach, which can be described in detail as follows.

3.5.3.1 Step 1: Load Configuration Settings

The framework's configuration settings are read from a JSON file, making it easy to change injections settings. These settings define parameters like:

- Image and annotations paths
- Cell size in computing unoccupied space for potential injections
- Max amount of injected thumbnails per image
- Remove background
- Use a 'smart' thumbnail selection
- Enable debugging mode

3.5.3.2 Step 2: Load Images, Annotations, and Thumbnails

Based on the configuration settings, load the following:

- Images: load all images *marked for training* from the specified directory. The annotation data is loaded as a corresponding CSV file containing all the images annotation data

Figure 3.6: High-level flow diagram of the injection process

- Thumbnails: load the thumbnails from specified target classes (e.g., "CIRAR," "PIBSA," "BRSOL"). These thumbnails are stored as individual image files

3.5.3.3 Step 3: Injecting Thumbnails Into Images

All images loaded for injection are iterated through. During an iteration, the topmost image in the stack is popped and a copy is created. The associated annotations for the image are loaded, and the unoccupied space in the image is computed by loading the existing bounding boxes of the image. The image is divided into a grid of cells (defined by the *cell size* in configuration), and a 2D matrix stores the availability of each cell. Cells occupied by existing bounding boxes are marked as unavailable for injection.

A random subset of thumbnails are selected from the loaded pool, limited by the *max injections per image* setting. If the option of using *smart thumbnail selection* is enabled, a pre-trained ResNet model assesses thumbnail quality, selecting only those surpassing a specific threshold. However, this functionality was not utilized in the results of this thesis, but was nevertheless developed for future potential thumbnail selection.

The framework attempts to inject each selected thumbnail into the image. A sliding window search, starting at a random cell, identifies a free space large enough to accommodate the thumbnail. If a viable position is found, the thumbnail is overlaid onto the full image. If the *remove background* is set, a background removal algorithm is applied to ensure seamless blending. The bounding boxes list is updated with the new annotation corresponding to the injected thumbnail, and the unoccupied cells matrix is modified accordingly. If no suitable position is found, the thumbnail is returned to the pool for potential injection into another image.

3.5.3.4 Step 4: Storing the Output

Finally, the injected image is saved to the output directory, and the newly generated annotations are appended to the output CSV file. This CSV file contains both original and injected annotations, distinguished by a field '*Injected*'.

3.5.4 Important Considerations for Thumbnail Placement

To guarantee the effectiveness of the thumbnail injection, several important aspects were considered during the decision-making strategy regarding placement:

- **Realistic Placement:** thumbnails should be placed in a way that makes sense within the image context, avoiding "impossible" locations if possible, as this could negatively affect the model's training. In other words, thumbnails should only be placed where they *could* naturally occur in the image (e.g. dirt).
- **Avoiding Overlap and Occlusion:** injected thumbnails **must not** overlap with existing bounding boxes or occlude other important objects in the image. This ensures that the integrity of the original annotations are preserved and prevents introducing misleading information into the

injected output data (e.g. the old annotation data is kept, but the contents are overlaid but another image).

- **Balanced Distribution:** the distribution of injected thumbnails should be balanced across regions within the images, which prevents the introduction of bias. For example, 10 injected thumbnails should not be placed in the top-left corner of every image just because it is intuitive to search the image from $(x = 0 \rightarrow x = w, y = 0 \rightarrow y = h)$.

The following subsections describe how the framework addresses these considerations.

3.5.5 Avoiding Overlap and Finding Free Positions for Injection

An essential requirement of the injection process is to ensure that injected thumbnails are not overlaid on top of existing bounding boxes. The framework employs a sliding window approach coupled with a grid-based representation of free space within the image, which is how the injections-process determines if a potential location is viable for injection.

3.5.5.1 Grid-Based Representation of Unoccupied Space

A grid-based approach was designed for finding free spaces was designed. A simple method could involve flagging all pixels inside the existing bounding boxes in the image, but this is extremely computationally expensive and inefficient.

To make an efficient approach that does not create a 1-to-1 width (w) times height (h), $w \cdot h$, matrix of pixels to denote occupied space, an adjustable grid was implemented. Creating a $w \cdot h$ matrix of the image would require $w \cdot h$ operations (one operation for every pixel in the image) to check for occupied space. This can be expressed as:

$$\text{operations}_{\text{full}} = \text{total}_{\text{pixels}} = w \cdot h \quad (3.2)$$

However, using a grid with a cell size of n pixels requires only:

$$\text{operations}_{\text{grid}} = \frac{w}{n} \cdot \frac{h}{n} = \frac{w \cdot h}{n^2} = \frac{\text{operations}_{\text{full}}}{n^2} \quad (3.3)$$

Thus significantly reducing the amount of operations needed for computing the unoccupied space by a factor, n^2 . Putting that into perspective, a $2448 \cdot 2048$ image would require $2448 \cdot 2048 = 5013504$ operations to check for occupied space for every pixel. By contrast, using a grid with a cell size of 25 pixels requires only $\frac{5013504}{25^2} = 8022$ operations.

Applying the grid-approach to find free regions of space for injection is shown in figure 3.7, where the image is divided into a 25-by-25 grid and the free space is computed and illustrated in red. Given the scale of up to ~ 60000

Figure 3.7: Illustration of grid overlay

potential images for injection, this reduction in computational load enables trading minimal detail complexity for significant computational efficiency.

Choosing an appropriate grid size is a trade-off between computational efficiency and level of detail complexity in finding free space. Figure 3.8 illustrates the effect of different grid sizes for the same raw image used in 3.7, where 3.8b is the same grid computation as used in 3.7b. Through experimentation, a value of 25px was found as a good balance between finding free space and increasing efficiency.

Figure 3.8: Comparison of different grid values

3.5.5.2 Balanced Distribution: Random Sliding Window Search

For each selected thumbnail, a sliding window search is run to find a viable injection position in the image. The window dimensions are determined by the width and height of the thumbnail, rounded up to nearest multiple of the cell size. The search begins at a *random* cell within the grid, to ensure no bias towards a certain area of the image and adhering to consideration of section 3.5.4. The window systematically slides across the grid, from left to right, wrapping around

to the next cell-row when hitting the edge, which ensures that every possible location is considered within the image.

3.5.5.3 Picking a Free Position

At each position, it is checked whether the window is entirely contained within free space, represented in list `unoccupied_cells_matrix`. Specifically, a position is deemed viable if:

- All cells within the window are marked as unoccupied, ensuring that the injected thumbnail will not overlap with any existing bounding boxes
- The window does not extend beyond the image dimensions, preventing the injected thumbnail from being partially cut off at the image edges

If a viable position is found, the thumbnail is injected into the image at that location. The corresponding bounding box annotation (`minX`, `maxX`, `minY`, `maxY`) is then added to the image's annotation data, and the `unoccupied_cells_matrix` is updated, reflecting the new occupied space. If no viable position is found after searching the entire grid, the thumbnail is returned to the pool for potential injection into another image.

The output images of an injection batch using the `debug` setting is shown in figure A.4, where original bounding boxes from the existing plant instances are shown in the grid size of $25px$ with the newly injected thumbnails, showing no overlaps, along with the non-debug output image. The full sized images are found appendix A.2.

Figure 3.9: Injected output images with `debug` configuration

3.5.6 Addressing Realistic Injection

Ensuring realistic placement of injected thumbnails is also a considerable aspect of the injection process. However, defining "realistic" is inherently complex due

Figure 3.10: Examples of grown weed images containing "Box" in filename

to the wide variability in field images, making finding generic parameters to look for challenging.

One approach to address this challenge was to exclude all images containing the string "Box" (of any permutation) in the filename. Images containing "Box" in their filename depict grown weeds, where plants are arranged within a box (see figure 3.10). These images contain a large amount of unoccupied space *outside the box*. Injecting thumbnails into these regions could lead to unrealistic placements that might confuse the YOLOv5 model during training. Other scenarios that could lead to unrealistic injections could be factors such as varied backgrounds, difficult lighting conditions, or something else.

While this strategy only provides a very simple consideration for realism, it is chosen simplification. A more thorough inspection of the images would be needed to identify other potentially unrealistic injection scenarios. However, this was not prioritized due to the time-constraints of the project.

3.5.7 Unused Functionality

While the core functionality of the injection framework uses random thumbnail selection and direct injection without background removal, two additional functionalities were developed but not utilized in this thesis: background removal and smart thumbnail selection.

The decision to not utilize these functionalities was a result of first and foremost examining the Injection Framework using original cutout thumbnails. Incorporating background removal and smart thumbnail selection would have introduced multiple layers of complexity to the experimentation process. Given the YOLOv5 model's training time of 8-9 days, a comprehensive evaluation of these additional features, while potentially beneficial, was deemed out of scope for this thesis. Priority was instead placed on establishing a robust baseline performance using the core Injection Framework with unaltered thumbnails.

3.5.7.1 Background Removal

The background removal function uses *Excess Green minus Excess Red Index (ExGR)* to isolate the plant from its original background, which a common technique in plant image processing[40]. Removing the background of the

thumbnails could potentially enhance the realism of injections by ensuring they blend seamlessly with the new background of the target image. However, initial testing showed that this approach can introduce artifacts into the injected images from parts of the plant not belonging to the thumbnail, as the ExGR algorithm may not perfectly segment the plant. This sometimes left behind fragments of the original background, as shown in figure 3.11

Figure 3.11: Example of injection with background removal and introduction of artifacts

3.5.7.2 Smart Thumbnail Selection

The smart thumbnail selection feature uses a pre-trained ResNet model to assess the quality of thumbnails before injection. This approach aims to select only high-quality thumbnails based on their visual clarity and representation of the target plant, potentially improving the effectiveness of the augmented dataset. This feature was not prioritized in this thesis due to the focus on evaluating the impact of the core injection framework with random thumbnail selection. However, smart thumbnail selection offers a promising direction for future work, particularly in exploring how varying thumbnail quality affects the YOLOv5 model's performance and whether a selection process can further improve model accuracy.

3.6 YOLOv5 Training, Evaluation and Injected Augmentation

This section describes the process of training and evaluating the YOLOv5 model, as well as how the injected dataset was created using the Thumbnail Injector Framework.

3.6.1 Creating the Injected Dataset

The Thumbnail Injection Framework was used to create a new dataset by augmenting existing images with approved thumbnails extracted from unapproved images. The target classes for injection were selected from I-GIS and Patriotisk Selskab's wishlist (full table in Appendix A.4), which includes classes they want the model to either become better at recognizing or introduce as entirely new classes:

- **Existing classes:** CIRAR, SPQOL, VICFX, SOLTU, PIBSA
- **New classes:** 1CRUF, 1POLF, 1SONG, GALAP, EQUAR, 1MATG, FUMOF, STEME, VIOAR, PAPRH, GERMO, CHEAL, SOLNI, 1LUPG, FAGES, 1RUMG, TAROF

Since only existing classes can be used for training, two batches of injected images were made with different target thumbnail classes. One class, *main batch*, produced injected images using the 5 *existing classes*, while the other *secondary batch* used the desired *new classes*. The *main* batch was used in experimentation, therefore the description going forward will relate to the creation of only the *main* batch.

As modifying the original dataset was not possible, and data integrity needed to be ensured, 5,000 images were independently and uniformly selected from the pool of images already "Marked for Training". The Thumbnail Injector Framework then injected thumbnails from the target classes into copies of these images, preserving the original annotations of the selected images. Initially, a total of 47,615 thumbnails were injected into the selected images, distributed across the main target classes as follows:

- CIRAR: 18,644
- SPQOL: 15,251
- VICFX: 10,997
- SOLTU: 1,519
- PIBSA: 1,204

This created an initial augmented dataset with a significant increase in the number of instances for these specific classes already used in training. However, challenges were encountered during the integration of these injected images into RoboWeedMaPS, which led to a reduction in the final number of thumbnails used for training.

3.6.1.1 Integrating Injected Images into RoboWeedMaPS

The RoboWeedMaPS platform is highly effective at managing new field images and annotations, however, it face some challenges when it comes to integrating pre-annotated images, such as those generated by the Thumbnail Injector Framework. The existing RoboWeedMaPS pipeline is primarily designed for uploading images of new fields, which lack pre-existing annotations, assuming that annotations are automatically assigned by CropWeed or by an expert after uploading.

However, an integrated part of the injected images is that they already contain annotations created by the Injector Framework. Directly importing these images with their associated annotations into the RoboWeedMaPS database is not possible due to the platform's structure. This made it necessary to employ a multi-step workaround approach to correctly integrate the injected images and their corresponding annotations into RoboWeedMaPS with the purpose of training the YOLOv5 model.

The workaround consisted of uploading the images to RoboWeedMaPS using an Upload Tool execution file, which is how new images must be added to RoboWeedMaPS. RoboWeedMaPS then assigns the images an UploadId and each image an individual ImageId. The current CropWeed model is then automatically used to predict the annotations of every image. To match the new ImageId's to the corresponding created images for and ensuring correct annotations, the new image annotations were fetched. Images were matched on FileName as the unique key, which was not changed by the RoboWeedMaPS upload procedure. To apply the annotation data output by the Injector Framework, all automatic annotations were deleted from the database. The scripts modifying the database (with redacted credentials) are available in the project repository at GitHub under "IGIS_DB"[38].

3.6.1.2 Mismatched Annotations When Updating

A significant challenge arose during the process of adding the premade injected annotations to the uploaded images in the RoboWeedMaPS database. Some of the images had inadvertently received duplicated annotations, meaning that a singular image contained annotations for two separate images. This is likely to have been an unintentional effect of sampling the "Marked for Training" images uniformly without deliberately checking for sampling the same image twice.

The RoboWeedMaPS upload tool seems to have handled the inputs as a set structure and only uploaded unique filenames, resulting in only one of the duplicated images being uploaded. It was technically possible to separate the annotations between the images with the same filename. However, it would require manual inspection of the applied annotations to determine which of the possible annotation lists was the right one for each image. Therefore, mitigation strategies were applied instead. Duplicates were found by analyzing the injected annotation data CSV file for gaps between the annotations of the same filename,

making them identifiable. All potentially duplicated images were flagged in the annotation data as **not** "Marked for Training" (`UseForTraining=0` in the database). The old annotation data was removed from the database, and the new updated annotation data was pushed.

3.6.1.3 Final Injected Dataset

After implementing these mitigation strategies, the final injected dataset used for YOLOv5 training consisted of 35524 injected thumbnails, which significantly less than the initial 47,615 due to the removal of duplicated images. The final distribution of injected thumbnails across the target classes was:

- CIRAR: 14009
- SPQOL: 11678
- VICFX: 7892
- SOLTU: 1117
- PIBSA: 828

The *main* batch of injected images were assigned `UploadId: 1633`. This contained a total of 1912 images with 1673 being flagged "Marked for Training": `UseForTraining=1` in the RoboWeedMaPS database.

3.6.2 YOLOv5 Training Configuration

The CropWeed training configurations was not modified in conjunction with this project, the regular training pipeline used by I-GIS was employed, merely including the additional injected data as `UploadId 1633`. The YOLOv5 model was utilized for both control and injected training experiments.

In the pipeline, the model is set to train 300 epochs with a batch size of 7 using the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimizer, however, I-GIS typically stops the training when it approaches convergence after a period of 7-9 days. Pre-trained weights from `YOLOv5l.pt` are used in initialization, and the initial learning rate is set to 0.01, with a final learning rate of 0.01. Momentum is set to 0.937 with a weight decay of 0.0005. A warm-up strategy is used for the first 3 epochs, with a warm-up momentum of 0.8 and a warm-up bias learning rate of 0.1. The input image sizes are set to 1600x1600. Training was performed on a PC with an NVIDIA RTX A5000 GPU using PyTorch 1.10 and CUDA 11.3. The full training configuration is available in Appendix A.5.

The data augmentations set in configuration are:

- Color Augmentations: Hue shift (0.015), Saturation shift (0.7), and Value shifts (0.4)

- Geometric Augmentations: Translation (0.1), Scaling (0.5), and Horizontal Flipping (0.5)
- YOLOv5 Specific Augmentations: Mosaic
 - Mosaic augmentation is enabled, meaning that during each training step, a new training image is created by combining four randomly chosen images into one to introduce variation.

3.6.2.1 YOLOv5 Evaluation Metrics

The performance of the trained YOLOv5 models was evaluated using the metrics described in section 2.3.3 on a test set that was not used during training. Mean Average Precision (mAP) was calculated at the Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds: mAP@0.5 (mAP50) and mAP@0.5:0.95 (mAP50-95), which is standard practice to provide a more comprehensive evaluation.

Chapter 4

Experiments and Results

This chapter presents the experiments conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed hierarchical classification approach using CropDiva and the Thumbnail Injection Framework in addressing class imbalance and data under-utilization in I-GIS RoboWeedMaPS dataset.

4.1 CropDiva Experiments and Results

The CropDiva model was trained using the configuration and parameters described in Section 3.4.2. This section presents the model's performance results on the test set, which was not used during training, along with the computed thresholds for re-labeling the "Dicot" class.

4.1.1 Model Performance

Figure 4.1 shows the confusion matrix of evaluating the trained CropDiva model, visualizing the model's classification performance on the test set. This matrix displays the predicted classes against the actual classes, which provides a clear assessment of the model's accuracy in distinguishing between different weed species.

Confusion matrix from dataset (test):													
	Predicted												
	1CHE	1CRU	1LUP	1URT	ATXP	FAGE	POLA	POLL	PPPM	VERP	VICF	VIDA	
0 1CHE	1763	4	3	0	7	9	3	2	0	7	7	1	0.976
b 1CRU	3	81	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	1	2	0	0.880
s 1LUP	5	0	1198	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0.993
e 1URT	0	0	0	85	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0.966
r ATXP	10	0	0	0	60	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0.789
v FAGE	18	5	1	0	1	6407	3	5	0	9	6	2	0.992
e POLA	7	0	2	0	0	2	279	1	0	0	0	2	0.952
d POLL	1	0	3	0	0	5	1	176	0	0	1	0	0.941
PPPM	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	387	0	1	0	0.990
VERP	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	376	0	1	0.987
VICF	4	3	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	588	0	0.980
VIDA	5	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	4	0	391	0.961
	0.970	0.835	0.990	0.988	0.870	0.995	0.959	0.951	0.997	0.940	0.970	0.982	0.984

Figure 4.1: Evaluation of the trained CropDiva model on test set

4.1.2 Threshold Computation and Selection

To ensure confident re-labeling of the "Dicot" thumbnails, optimal and median thresholds were computed for each class based on the model's performance on

the test set, as described in section 3.4.3. The computed precision-recall curves are shown in figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Precision-Recall curves for the test set evaluation

Table 4.1 shows the computed thresholds, along with the number of instances for each class (Thr_{opt}). The optimal and median thresholds are denoted, Thr_{opt} and Thr_{med} , respectively. Precision and recall are computed as described in section 3.4.3, which are used to compute the associated F1 scores. The mean and standard deviation of the confidence scores for correctly classified instances were also computed, which can be seen in table A.1 of Appendix A.3.

EPPO	N	Thr_{opt}	Thr_{med}	N_{opt}	P	R	F1
1CHEG	1806	0.999990	0.999994	11	1.0	0.090255	0.165567
1CRUF	92	0.975467	0.999104	55	1.0	0.673913	0.805195
1LUPG	1207	0.991039	0.999545	414	1.0	0.903065	0.949064
1URTF	88	0.979282	0.999458	70	1.0	0.829545	0.906832
ATXPA	76	0.981922	0.997869	34	1.0	0.460526	0.630630
FAGES	6457	0.995719	0.999104	1355	1.0	0.868825	0.929809
POLAV	293	0.999859	0.999932	33	1.0	0.139932	0.245509
POLLA	187	0.983953	0.999594	134	1.0	0.844920	0.915942
PPPMM	391	0.997392	0.999767	263	1.0	0.918159	0.957334
VERPE	381	0.992547	0.999537	269	1.0	0.811024	0.895652
VICFX	600	0.997329	0.999744	228	1.0	0.740000	0.850575
VIOAR	407	0.938825	0.999118	326	1.0	0.894349	0.944228

Table 4.1: Computed thresholds using the trained CropDiva model (without μ and σ)

The trained CropDiva model was used to predict the labels of all unapproved thumbnails in the I-GIS dataset, especially with the purpose of investigating the predictions of "Dicots". The predictions were stored in a CSV file with the following fields: "OriginalPlantId", "UploadId", "ImageId", "ID", "PredictedPlantId", "ClassificationScore", and "AboveThreshold", with each row containing the identifier and prediction for one thumbnail.

The "AboveThreshold" column indicates whether the classification score ("ClassificationScore") were greater than or equal to the computed optimal threshold for the corresponding predicted class ("PredictedPlantId"), which was used to re-label the thumbnails. The complete file is available as `predictions_unlabeled_with_approval.csv` under `preprocessing/igis_cropdiva/csv/` in the GitHub repository[38].

4.2 YOLOv5 Experiments and Results

This section presents the results of the YOLOv5 experiments conducted to evaluate the impact of the Thumbnail Injection Framework on the model's performance. Two experiments were conducted:

- **Training 0 (Control)**: a control training using only the original "Marked for Training" images
- **Training 1 (Injected)**: an injected training using both the original "Marked for Training" images and the injected images of `UploadId 1633` (detailed in section 3.6.1.3)

4.2.1 YOLOv5 Model Training and Evaluation

Both the control and injected training experiments used the training setup described in section 3.6, including the hyper-parameters and data augmentation techniques. The models were evaluated on the dedicated test set configured, which was not used during training, ensuring an unbiased assessment of their performances.

Table 4.2 presents the evaluation metrics for the YOLOv5 model trained on the original "Marked for Training" dataset. The metrics include precision, recall, F1 score, mAP@0.5, and mAP@0.5:0.95 for each class, including the aggregated performance across all classes.

Table 4.3 presents the evaluation metrics for the YOLOv5 model trained on the augmented injected dataset, incorporating both the original images and the injected images.

The generated evaluation results from the trainings can be found in appendix A.6, including confusion matrices (figures A.6 and A.11), F1-confidence curves (A.7 and A.12), Precision-confidence curves (A.8 and A.13), Recall-confidence curves (A.9 and A.14), and Precision-Recall (A.10 and A.15).

Class	Images	Instances	P	R	mAP50	mAP50-95
all	5171	208574	0.78	0.774	0.785	0.557
PPPM	5171	40320	0.783	0.64	0.72	0.447
PPPD	5171	146002	0.868	0.797	0.86	0.631
VICFX	5171	2658	0.878	0.854	0.892	0.693
PIBSA	5171	1066	0.863	0.831	0.872	0.575
ZEAMX	5171	2078	0.863	0.797	0.895	0.701
SOLTU	5171	448	0.42	0.745	0.383	0.256
SPQOL	5171	1512	0.8	0.809	0.841	0.607
BEAVA	5171	2539	0.766	0.9	0.825	0.648
CIRAR	5171	2060	0.748	0.742	0.779	0.581
BRSOL	5171	2894	0.941	0.964	0.981	0.862
FAGES	5171	858	0.745	0.599	0.727	0.426
1LUPG	5171	216	0.715	0.718	0.736	0.504
PSEZ	5171	5923	0.753	0.671	0.698	0.31

Table 4.2: Control training (regular dataset)

Class	Images	Instances	P	R	mAP50	mAP50-95
all	5682	241435	0.834	0.823	0.838	0.657
PPPM	5682	44050	0.809	0.61	0.702	0.436
PPPD	5682	167712	0.883	0.79	0.859	0.636
VICFX	5682	2945	0.903	0.886	0.914	0.778
PIBSA	5682	1231	0.842	0.75	0.784	0.487
ZEAMX	5682	2333	0.901	0.818	0.906	0.722
SOLTU	5682	639	0.52	0.793	0.518	0.381
SPQOL	5682	3381	0.815	0.866	0.9	0.753
BEAVA	5682	2603	0.766	0.896	0.817	0.629
CIRAR	5682	3616	0.842	0.855	0.9	0.787
BRSOL	5682	3229	0.946	0.961	0.979	0.86
FAGES	5682	2861	0.915	0.884	0.955	0.877
1LUPG	5682	531	0.917	0.913	0.952	0.884
PSEZ	5682	6304	0.777	0.672	0.708	0.315

Table 4.3: Training 1 (Injected) training (regular dataset AND injected images)

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Analysis of CropDiva Results and Addressing RQ1

This section analyzes the performance of the CropDiva model, focusing on its ability to re-label the broad "Monocot" and "Dicot" classes and address the class imbalance problem in the RoboWeedMaPS dataset to answer RQ1.

5.1.1 Trained CropDiva Model Performance

As seen in the confusion matrix, figure 4.1, the trained CropDiva model achieved a high overall accuracy on the test set, achieving a 98.4% overall accuracy on unseen data. This demonstrates a strong ability for the model to differentiate between different weed and crop species, meaning it has a good ability to generalize.

Examining the confusion matrix (figure 4.1), it is clear that the model correctly classified instances of various classes with high precision and recall. In regards to RQ1, this indicates that the trained CropDiva model can effectively identify specific plant species within the trained classes, confirming accurate classification. This forms the basis for **confident** re-labeling of the more general "Monocot" and "Dicot" classes into one of the trained classes.

5.1.2 Threshold Selection and Trade-Off of Precision and Recall

To ensure high confidence in the re-labeling process, both optimal and median thresholds were computed for each class. The optimal threshold ensures *perfect precision* ($P = 1.0$) on the test set, which minimizes the risk of falsely re-labeling thumbnails as a specific plant class when they are actually another. This aligns with the objective of refining class labels **confidently** without introducing errors.

As seen in Table 4.1, the optimal threshold often results in a lower recall (R), which is expected as precision is prioritized to avoid misclassifications. However, "1CHEG" has a recall value of ~ 0.09 , which is significantly lower than other classes. This could suggest that while the model is very accurate when it does predict "1CHEG" instances, it is likely missing many actual instances of this class. One reason for this could be that "1CHEG" is sharing visual characteristics with other species, which would make it hard for the model to differentiate between them - especially at high confidence levels.

A low recall in terms of re-labeling "Monocot" or "Dicot" into more specific classes means that while the re-labeled instances would be highly reliable, a large portion of thumbnails that potentially belongs to other classes would remain

as "Monocot" or "Dicot". Although this aligns with the desired properties of re-labeling without human intervention, it is important to acknowledge the trade-off between precision and recall. The employed approach of $P = 1.0$ is rather *greedy*, as it prioritizes the accuracy of re-labeled instances over maximizing the number of re-labeled thumbnails. Table 4.1 shows that a substantial number of thumbnails, as indicated by the N_{opt} , could still be confidently re-labeled for most classes (in the test set), which actually highlights the model's ability to make highly reliable predictions even with a *greedy* re-labeling strategy.

For limited data, the median threshold cutoff could offer a more balanced approach by considering the distribution of confidence scores for correctly classified instances. This strategy could instead allow for a higher number of "Dicot" thumbnails to be re-labeled, increasing the representation of specific weed species in the dataset. However, using the median threshold would also increase the risk of misclassifications compared to the optimal threshold. This again brings up the trade-off between maximizing the number of re-labeled thumbnails and minimizing potential errors, which should be decided based on the task and objective.

5.1.3 Predictions on Unapproved Monocot and Dicot Samples

The trained CropDiva model was applied to predict the labels of 169,572 unapproved thumbnails within the CropDiva dataset, with a particular focus on the 123,824 "Dicot" (PPDD) and 4,625 "Monocot" (PPMM) thumbnails. Using the computed optimal thresholds, the model was used to re-label a significant portion of these thumbnails into more specific weed classes.

Table 5.1 shows the total number of re-labeled "Monocot" and "Dicot" with their re-labeled classes. As seen in the table, the model was able to confidently re-label 26.7% of the "Dicot" class into other classes. 26,105 of the 'Dicot' instances were re-labeled as 'FAGES', which is a substantial amount compared to the other re-labeled classes. This could likely be due to the distribution of classes within the CropDiva training data, where 'FAGES' is the most represented with 43,558 instances (see section 3.4.2.2), which is considerably more than any other class. Additionally, 3,207 "Dicot" instances were re-labeled as "PPMM", suggesting that some thumbnails were initially misclassified as "Dicot".

The re-labeling of "Monocot" instances, although less substantial in volume, also demonstrates the effectiveness of the hierarchical classification approach. An overwhelming percentage of the re-labeled "Monocot" thumbnails (1,926) were confidently re-labeled as "Monocot", suggesting the need to exclude the dominant class from the training set. This is probably because the "Monocot" class encompasses a variety of classes, making it easy for the classifier to predict it, as it has a broader feature representation.

Re-labeled EPPO	Monocot (PPPMM)	Dicot (PPPDD)
FAGES	89	26105
PPPMM	1926	3207
VIOAR	2	1788
VERPE	-	699
1URTF	8	676
1LUPG	23	400
POLLA	-	126
VICFX	-	38
1CRUF	-	26
ATXPA	-	14
1CHEG	-	10
POLAV	-	3

Table 5.1: Predicted Counts of the unapproved 'Monocot's and 'Dicot's

5.1.4 Addressing RQ1: Achieving Hierarchical Refinement

The results clearly illustrated the effectiveness of using the trained CropDiva model to refine the "Monocot" and "Dicot" categories to tackle the hierarchical classification problem present in the RoboWeedMaPS dataset. By utilizing the model and computed optimal threshold to confidently distinguish specific classes, a significant portion of the broad "Dicot" classes were automatically re-labeled into more precise categories, as seen in table 5.1. This re-labeling process directly addresses the challenge of class imbalance in the dataset by enhancing the representation of less frequent weed classes without requiring the manual annotation. The strict precision requirement of $P = 1.0$ to compute the optimal threshold ensures that the re-labelings are reliable.

This automated re-labeling process aligns perfectly with the objectives of RQ1. It showcases the practical use of a trained classification model, in this case using the CropDiva framework, in refining hierarchical labels, thereby creating a more nuanced and rich dataset for tasks in precision agriculture.

5.1.4.1 Applying CropDiva to the YOLOv5 Training Dataset

While the analysis has focused on refining the 'Monocot' and 'Dicot' within a subset of the RoboWeedMaPS dataset, the approach is applicable to the refine the entire RoboWeedMaPS dataset used for training the YOLOv5 model. By leveraging the trained CropDiva model and the computed optimal thresholds, I-GIS can effectively and automatically re-label a considerable portion of the "Dicot" and "Monocot" annotations within their training images. This would directly address the class imbalance problem by enriching the representation of less frequent weed species, which is probable to improve the YOLOv5 model's performance as a result. As learned from the re-labeling of "Dicots" into FAGES, the ability to detect and classify a wider range of weeds with greater accuracy

could be directly proportional to the amount of thumbnails used to train the CropDiva model. This suggests that training a CropDiva model on the entire approved RoboWeedMaPS dataset, excluding "Monocot" and "Dicot", these broad classes could be heavily diluted and effectively re-labeled.

5.1.4.2 Limitations and Future Directions for RQ1

While this hierarchical refinement strategy using CropDiva proves effective, there are some limitations and future directions to consider. The CropDiva model was trained on a subset of the data from a single field, "F6" from Flakkebjerg. While it demonstrates good performance on unseen data from that field, its performance on images from other fields with potentially different plant distributions and image conditions would require further investigation. Although the optimal threshold computed guarantees perfect precision, it also results in low recall. Perhaps alternative threshold selection techniques, such as using ROC curves or cost-sensitive learning, could be explored to find an acceptable trade-off between the number of re-labeled thumbnails and minimizing misclassifications.

Future work should most importantly explore training a CropDiva model on the entire approved RoboWeedMaPS dataset to investigate the potential of the shown approach.

5.2 Analysis of YOLOv5 Training Results

This section provides a structured analysis of the experimental results, directly comparing the performance of the YOLOv5 models from Training 0 (Control), T_0 , with the original dataset and Training 1 (injected), T_1 , with the injected dataset. Focus will be to examine the Thumbnail Injection Framework's impact on the targeted injected classes: CIRAR, SPQOL, VICFX, SOLTU, and PIBSA.

5.2.1 Direct Comparison of Control and Injected Training

To better understand how the two training's evaluation results differ, table 5.2 presents a direct comparison of the evaluation metrics for the two YOLOv5 models trained from T_0 and T_1 using the evaluation metrics for each injected class and the aggregated performance across all classes.

Analyzing table 5.2 shows that training with the injected dataset significantly boosted the model's performance across several categories, especially for CIRAR (Creeping Thistle) and SOLTU (Potato). To interpret these evaluation results even better, examining the increase in total thumbnails used are also an interesting factor, shown in table 5.3. The table also depicts the percentage of explicitly "Approved" thumbnails compared to the implicit "*approved*" thumbnails in the original dataset. These thumbnails are not flagged "Approved", however the images they are present in has been allowing for use in training.

Class	Metric	T0 (Control)	T1 (Injected)	Improvement
CIRAR +14009 injected	P	0.748	0.842	+12.6%
	R	0.742	0.855	+15.2%
	F1	0.745	0.848	+13.8%
	mAP50	0.779	0.900	+15.5%
	mAP50-95	0.581	0.787	+35.5%
SPQOL +11678 injected	P	0.800	0.815	+1.9%
	R	0.809	0.866	+7.0%
	F1	0.804	0.840	+4.5%
	mAP50	0.841	0.900	+7.0%
	mAP50-95	0.607	0.753	+24.0%
VICFX +7892 injected	P	0.878	0.903	+2.8%
	R	0.854	0.886	+3.7%
	F1	0.866	0.894	+3.2%
	mAP50	0.892	0.914	+2.5%
	mAP50-95	0.693	0.778	+12.3%
SOLTU +1117 injected	P	0.420	0.520	+23.8%
	R	0.745	0.793	+6.4%
	F1	0.536	0.628	+17.2%
	mAP50	0.383	0.518	+35.2%
	mAP50-95	0.256	0.381	+48.8%
PIBSA +828 injected	P	0.863	0.842	-2.4%
	R	0.831	0.750	-9.7%
	F1	0.847	0.793	-6.4%
	mAP50	0.872	0.784	-10.1%
	mAP50-95	0.575	0.487	-15.3%
All	mAP50	0.785	0.838	+6.8%
	mAP50-95	0.557	0.657	+17.9%

Table 5.2: Direct comparison of YOLOv5 model’s performance on the test set of T0 and T1

Class	T0 Appr. [%]	T0 (Control)	T1 (Injected)	Inc. [%]
CIRAR	94.80%	19689	33698	71.15%
SPQOL	29.66%	17494	29172	66.68%
VICFX	84.88%	20550	28442	38.41%
SOLTU	90.51%	5433	6550	20.57%
PIBSA	100.00%	10654	11482	7.87%

Table 5.3: Total thumbnail representation for target classes in both trainings

To get an even better understanding of how the training data changes affected performance, examining the percentage changes in thumbnail representation and performance for each targeted class provides valuable insights.

5.2.1.1 Analysis of Individual Class Performance

For CIRAR (Creeping Thistle), the injection added 14,009 thumbnails, increasing the total CIRAR instances from 19,689 to 33,698, which is a significant 71.15% increase. This substantial augmentation resulted in a +35.5% improvement in $\text{mAP}@0.5:0.95$. Notably, the original dataset already had a high percentage (94.80%) of explicitly "Approved" CIRAR thumbnails. This suggests a strong correlation between the increased representation of CIRAR and the model's increased performance for this class, which supports the hypothesis that adding additional "Approved" from unused images better the model's performance for that class.

In the case of SPQOL (Spinach), the injection added 11,678 SPQOL thumbnails, representing a 66.68.% increase in the total number of instances used in training. This augmentation led to a +24.0% improvement in $\text{mAP}@0.5:0.95$. In contrast to CIRAR, the original dataset had a lower percentage (29.66%) of explicitly "Approved" SPQOL thumbnails. This means that a significant portion of the SPQOL thumbnails used for training in the original dataset (T_0) is based on implicit "approval", meaning that experts has not explicitly verified them but has deemed the images containing these thumbnails acceptable for training. The positive performance gains, despite the relatively lower initial proportion of "Approved" SPQOL instances, could indicate that the Thumbnail Injection Framework is effective in supplementing the existing dataset with useful information for the model's abilities - even for classes with a lower initial number of explicitly approved instances.

For VICFX (Faba Bean), the injection added 7,892 VICFX thumbnails, a 48.05% increase in the total number of instances used for training. This resulted in a +12.3% improvement in $\text{mAP}@0.5:0.95$, but the increase in the number of instances was smaller compared to CIRAR and SPQOL (38.41%). This could suggest that the model's performance may be more sensitive to the initial amount of data for some classes. While a considerable increase in data is still beneficial, the impact in performance may be less pronounced if the initial dataset is already relatively well-represented.

SOLTU, despite a smaller number of injected thumbnails (1,117), had the most significant performance improvements terms, with a 35.2% improvement in $\text{mAP}@0.5$ and a 48.8% improvement in $\text{mAP}@0.5:0.95$. The total number of SOLTU thumbnails used in training increased by 20.5% from 5,433 to 6,550. Although the percentage increase in thumbnails is smaller for SOLTU than CIRAR, the substantial improvement in performance for SOLTU could be attributed to the model learning notably better feature representations for SOLTU given the small amount of total data samples in the training set.

For the least injected class, PIBSA (Field Pea), the injected training T_1 resulted in a decrease in performance, particularly in $\text{mAP}@0.5:0.95$ (-15.3%) unlike the other classes. This could be due to the quality or the distribution of injected thumbnails for PIBSA that may not have been as effective as for other classes. It is important to note as well that PIBSA had a relatively high number of

thumbnails in the original training set (10,654). The increase of only 828 might not have been sufficient to significantly impact the model's learning for this already well-represented class, and instead confuse the model more than benefit it.

However this unexpected outcome could also be due to the fact that PIBSA already had a 100% percentage of "Approved" thumbnails in the original dataset. The injection may have introduced an imbalance, making it harder to learn the features of PIBSA. While the injection appears to have helped the other target classes, this might be due to the fact that they have a percentage of explicitly "Approved" thumbnails lower than 100%, resulting in the injected thumbnails improving feature representations. However, for PIBSA with a 100% "Approved" thumbnails in the original dataset, this could suggest that the injected instances instead worsens the feature representation.

Overall, the results suggest that the Thumbnail Injection Framework has been effective in improving the performance of the YOLOv5 model for the targeted classes with limited or imbalanced data representations. The injected augmentation showed particularly valuable for classes like SOLTU (Potato), where data scarcity was a significant challenge in the original dataset.

5.2.2 Assessing the Thumbnail Injector Framework

RQ2 aimed to explore if methodologies could be developed to utilize the approved thumbnails from images not approved for YOLO training. This proposed methodology for exploration was further defined in section 2.5.2, refining the research question to whether a robust and context-aware thumbnail injector framework could be designed and implemented to augment approved images with thumbnails from the partially approved images. Additionally, the framework should ensure realistic and consistent integration of thumbnails while avoiding issues like overlapping and occlusion.

5.2.2.1 Design and Implementation

The Thumbnail Injector Framework, as detailed in Section 3.5.1, successfully achieved the design objectives outlined in RQ2. To address *robustness and Context awareness*, the framework incorporated a grid-based strategy for finding unoccupied spaces and used a sliding window search for finding suitable positions for injection. This approach ensured consistent and realistic placement of thumbnails by avoiding overlaps with existing annotations and respecting image boundaries, as well as *avoiding overlap and occlusion*. The debug mode visually confirmed the absence of overlaps (figure A.4). Measures taken for ensuring *realistic integration* to minimize unrealistic placements were minimal, such as excluding images with "Box" in their filenames. While being a basic approach, it addressed a specific type of unrealistic injection scenario. Future work should expand on this by incorporating more sophisticated realism checks and image samplings.

5.2.2.2 Impact on YOLOv5 Performance

The analysis of the YOLOv5 training results above provides strong evidence that the Thumbnail Injector Framework can successfully improve the model's performance for certain classes by augmenting the dataset. Four of five injected classes showed notable improvements, as the injected training ($T1$) resulted in substantial improvements in $mAP@0.5:0.95$ for: CIRAR, SPQOL, VICFX, and SOLTU. This strongly suggests that the injected thumbnails provided valuable additional training data for these classes. However, the performance decrease for PIBSA highlights the need for further improvements and examinations into the specific characteristics of the injected thumbnails and their potential impact on model training - especially for classes with a very high percentage explicitly "Approved" instances in the original dataset.

5.2.2.3 Addressing RQ2

Based on the design, implementation, and impact on YOLOv5 performance, it can be confidently concluded that RQ2 has been successfully addressed. The Thumbnail Injector Framework effectively augmented the dataset by utilizing approved thumbnails from partially annotated images, ensuring realistic integration and avoiding overlaps. The positive impact on the YOLOv5 model's performance for four of out five target classes demonstrates the framework's ability to enhance the training data.

However, the case of PIBSA highlights the need for further refinement and improvements of additional factors, such as thumbnail selection, injection strategy, and data balance.

5.2.3 Limitations and Future Directions for RQ2

While the framework in its current form provides a strong foundation for leveraging partially annotated data, future work should investigate these nuances to further improve its effectiveness and ability to generalize. Additionally, several limitations were identified that are important to address.

5.2.3.1 Overlapping Annotations in Thumbnails

Upon inspection of the injected images uploaded to RoboWeedMaPS, a pitfall was identified in the thumbnail extraction process. The current implementation successfully extracts thumbnails based on bounding box coordinates, however it overlooks a crucial pitfall: overlapping annotations.

As observed in the original I-GIS dataset, bounding boxes frequently overlap, which is acceptable for the original annotation purpose. However, during thumbnail extraction, this overlap leads to partial plant instances in the cutouts. When a bounding box used for extraction partially overlaps with another bounding box, the extracted thumbnail *only* contain a the fragment of the secondary plant that is present inside the indented crop-out bounding box.

This creates an unrealistic representation of the plant, potentially confusing the YOLOv5 model during training. This phenomenon is shown in figure 5.1, which is an example from the injected dataset used in $T1$.

(a) Crop

(b) Crop with marked double instances

Figure 5.1: Multiple plant instances in the same injected thumbnail

Additionally, the presence of other plants within the extracted thumbnail is not accounted for in the annotations, thereby introducing a potential conflict between the visual content of the thumbnail and its corresponding label. This could potentially hinder the model's ability to learn accurate feature representations for the injected classes.

To mitigate this in future work and ensuring integrity of injected thumbnails, two strategies can be implemented. A straightforward approach to address this would be to modify the thumbnail extraction process to exclude *any* thumbnails containing overlapping bounding boxes. This would ensure that only thumbnails with a single, complete plant instance are injected, which eliminates the problem of partial plants in thumbnails. However, this could considerably reduce the number of thumbnails for injection, especially in datasets with a high density among the weeds and crops.

Another method could be to keep the thumbnails with overlapping annotations, but addressing the problematic regions instead. This could be achieved by replacing the overlapping areas with a background texture extracted from the original image (e.g. dirt), effectively masking the partially plant instances present in the extracted thumbnail. This approach would maintain a substantially higher number of thumbnails for injection compared to the strict exclusion criteria. However, it also requires a robust mechanism for identifying and accurately replacing the overlapping regions with a piece of neutral "background".

5.2.3.2 Duplicated Images and Annotations

As mentioned in section 3.6.1, the images used to create the injected dataset consist of images and annotations from the original dataset. Since these "Marked

for Training" were used, the injected dataset inherently includes duplicates of the sampled images and their original annotations. This duplication could potentially lead to overfitting of the included instances, in which the model becomes too specialized in recognizing the patterns from the duplicated images. While modifying the original images directly would have been ideal, it was not feasible in this project due to constraints with the RoboWeedMaPS dataset. Future work could address this storing a backup of the original images and modifying the images directly, avoiding having duplicates in the training set. Alternatively, images without pre-existing annotations could be used for injection, such as dirt texture.

5.2.3.3 Potential of Background Removal

The functionality of removing thumbnail backgrounds was not used, exploring this functionality further could potentially enhance the realism of injections by making the plant instances blend seamlessly with the target image's background. However, initial testing revealed challenges of artifacts in these attempts. The employed method of Excess Green minus Excess Red Index (ExGR) is commonly used in plant image processing and segmentation, however in this case, it requires the perfect segmentation of the plant. Although a challenge, by exploring more advanced segmentation techniques or refining the current ExGR method, it could potentially reduce the produced artifacts and create more realistic thumbnail injections, which could potentially improve the YOLOv5 model's ability to generalize. A trade-off between keeping and removing the background could instead be applying a gradient opacity to the thumbnail. However, an investigation into the background's effect of thumbnails should also be examined in the same context. While not area needing the most utmost addressing in regards to future work, it remains an interesting area to explore.

5.2.3.4 Data Loss and Mismatched Annotations

The challenges faced with integrating the injected images into RoboWeedMaPS, especially the issue of same filenames and the resulting data loss, offers valuable insights for future work. RoboWeedMaPS is currently limited in its pipeline for handling pre-annotated images, which could suggest revising the injected workflow to accommodate for this. Implementing a well-defined workflow for integrating external data into RoboWeedMaPS could also enable easier future research project.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Future Work

This chapter summarizes the key findings and contributions of the thesis, which addressed the class imbalance and data under-utilization challenges in improving the performance of I-GIS's YOLOv5 object detection model (CropWeed) for weed and crop recognition. It also presents the future research that should be prioritized to further enhance the approaches proposed.

6.1 Conclusion

This thesis investigated methods for improving the performance of I-GIS's YOLOv5 object detection model, CropWeed, used for weed and crop recognition in their precision agriculture platform, RoboWeedMaPS. The primary challenges addressed were class imbalance, which were dominated by the broad "Monocot" and "Dicot" categories, and the under-utilization of annotated data present in partially approved images.

To address the first research question (RQ1), the research successfully demonstrated the effectiveness of a hierarchical classification approach using the CropDiva model to refine the broad "Monocot" and "Dicot" labels into more specific weed classes. By training CropDiva on a chosen subset of the RoboWeedMaPS dataset, excluding the "Dicot" class to prevent bias. Utilizing a strict optimal threshold for prediction confidence, ensuring a precision of 1.0, 26.7% of "Dicot" thumbnails were confidently re-labeled. This automated process successfully increased the representation of less frequent weed classes, addressing the class imbalance challenge without requiring manual re-annotation.

For the second research question (RQ2), this thesis introduced a novel Thumbnail Injection Framework designed to leverage approved thumbnails from partially approved images. The framework successfully integrated these thumbnails into fully approved images, augmenting the training dataset while preserving data integrity and avoiding overlaps and occlusions. YOLOv5 training results showed notable improvements in mAP@0.5:0.95 for four out of five injected classes (CIRAR, SPQOL, VICFX, and SOLTU), demonstrating the framework's ability to enhance the YOLOv5 model's performance for classes with limited data.

The key contributions from this thesis are:

- Demonstrated the effectiveness of hierarchical classification using CropDiva for refining broad plant categories in I-GIS's dataset
- Developed a robust and context-aware Thumbnail Injection Framework to leverage partially annotated data effectively

- Showcased performance improvements in the YOLOv5 model for specific weed classes through injected data augmentation

6.2 Future Work

6.2.1 CropDiva

To improve the CropDiva model's performance and robustness, increasing the utilized training dataset by including images from various fields could enhance the model's ability to generalize. By incorporating a wider range of field conditions and weed species, the model's ability to accurately classify and refine labels across the entire RoboWeedMaPS dataset could be enhanced. In short, training the model on a larger and more diverse dataset could in turn ensure that the hierarchical classification approach remains effective when applied to new and unseen data.

Although the current approach of using a strict optimal threshold based on perfect precision ($P = 1.0$) has proven effective in ensuring the reliability of re-labeled thumbnails, it may result in a lower number of re-labeled instances. To achieve a more balanced trade-off between precision and recall, alternative threshold selection techniques could be explored, for example using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves or cost-sensitive learning methods to help identify thresholds that can maximize the number of re-labeled thumbnails while maintaining an acceptable level of accuracy. This could further optimize the hierarchical classification approach without sacrificing the quality of the re-labeled data.

6.2.2 Thumbnail Injection Framework

A critical limitation identified was the issue of overlapping annotations in extracted thumbnails. Future iterations of the framework should implement strategies to handle this, either by excluding thumbnails containing overlapping bounding boxes entirely or by developing a method to mask or replace the overlapping regions with neutral background textures (e.g. dirt) from the original image. Excluding overlapping thumbnails would ensure that only complete plant instances are injected, which maintains data integrity. However, this might significantly reduce the number of thumbnails available for injection. Instead, developing a robust technique for masking could address this limitation while also mitigating the risk of introducing misleading information into the training data.

Another major concern identified was the duplication of images and their original annotations in the injected dataset, which results from the framework's reliance on sampling images from the existing "Marked for Training" pool. This duplication could lead to overfitting, where the model becomes overly specialized in recognizing patterns from the duplicated instances, thereby reducing its ability to generalize to unseen data. Future iterations of the framework should prioritize

addressing this issue. This could be by exploring the feasibility of modifying the original "Marked for Training" images directly (and storing a backup), or making duplicates but not including the original images in the training. Additionally, images without annotations could be utilized as background images for injections.

6.2.3 Combining CropDiva and Thumbnail Injection

A interesting direction for future research lies in combining the approaches of both CropDiva and the Thumbnail Injection Framework for iterative dataset refinement and potentially new class introduction.

A pipeline could be implemented where CropDiva's predictions guide the re-labeling of thumbnails extracted from unapproved images, providing the Thumbnail Injector with additional approved thumbnails for injection, which could be introduced into the training set. Additionally, using CropDiva to iteratively dilute the "Monocot" and "Dicot" classes, while bettering the YOLOv5 model with injections. This iterative process would gradually refine the dataset, reducing the dominance of "Monocot" and "Dicot" categories while increasing the representation of specific weed species. This could potentially enable the introduction of new classes into the CropWeed model.

This combined approach offers a powerful strategy for tackling class imbalance, improving model performance, and expanding the crop and weed recognition capabilities of RoboWeedMaPS. It might not even be necessary to re-label all "Monocot" and "Dicot" instances. If CropDiva reduces their dominance sufficiently, strategic injection of thumbnails for specific classes could perhaps prove sufficient for training an effective model with *new* classes.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 GitHub Repository

The GitHub repository containing all public available code can be found at: https://github.com/heltechael/injector_tool.

A.2 Injected Images Example

Figure A.1: Image example 1 with debugging

Figure A.2: Image example 1 without debugging

Figure A.3: Image example 2 with debugging

Figure A.4: Image example 2 without debugging

A.3 CropDiva Results

EPPO	N	mu	sigma
1CHEG	1806	0.000554	0.008284
1CRUF	92	0.010870	0.049578
1LUPG	1207	0.000829	0.008514
1URTF	88	0.011364	0.024934
ATXPA	76	0.013158	0.042878
FAGES	6457	0.000155	0.008603
POLAV	293	0.003413	0.012509
POLLA	187	0.005348	0.017227
PPPM	391	0.002558	0.003413
VERPE	381	0.002625	0.005586
VICFX	600	0.001667	0.014954
VIOAR	407	0.002457	0.016562

Table A.1: Computed mu and sigma values using the trained CropDiva model

A.5 YOLOv5 Detailed Training Configuration

opt.yaml:

```
weights: pre_t/yolov5l.pt
cfg: ''
data: /media/tbrain2/Storage/TrainingSessions/Annotator/2024-05-13
      _14-52-28/data/dataset.yaml
hyp:
  lr0: 0.01
  lrf: 0.01
  momentum: 0.937
  weight_decay: 0.0005
  warmup_epochs: 3.0
  warmup_momentum: 0.8
  warmup_bias_lr: 0.1
  box: 0.05
  cls: 0.5
  cls_pw: 1.0
  obj: 1.0
  obj_pw: 1.0
  iou_t: 0.2
  anchor_t: 4.0
  fl_gamma: 0.0
  hsv_h: 0.015
  hsv_s: 0.7
  hsv_v: 0.4
  degrees: 0.0
  translate: 0.1
  scale: 0.5
  shear: 0.0
  perspective: 0.0
  flipud: 0.0
  fliplr: 0.5
  mosaic: 1.0
  mixup: 0.0
  copy_paste: 0.0
epochs: 300
batch_size: 7
imgsz: 1600
rect: false
resume: false
nosave: false
noval: false
noautoanchor: false
noplots: false
```

```
evolve: null
bucket: ''
cache: null
image_weights: false
device: '1'
multi_scale: false
single_cls: false
optimizer: SGD
sync_bn: false
workers: 8
project: ../../../../YoloV5RWM/runs/train
name: igis_2024-05-13_14-52-28
exist_ok: false
quad: false
cos_lr: false
label_smoothing: 0.0
patience: 100
freeze:
- 0
save_period: -1
seed: 0
local_rank: -1
entity: null
upload_dataset: false
bbox_interval: -1
artifact_alias: latest
save_dir: ../../../../YoloV5RWM/runs/train/igis_2024-05-13_
          14-52-28
```

A.6 All YOLOv5 Training Outputs

A.6.1 Training 0 (Control)

Figure A.6: Confusion Matrix for Training 0 (Control)

Figure A.7: F1-confidence curve for Training 0 (Control)

Figure A.8: Precision-confidence curve for Training 0 (Control)

Figure A.9: Recall-confidence curve for Training 0 (Control)

Figure A.10: Precision-Recall curve for Training 0 (Control)

A.6.2 Training 1 (Injected)

Figure A.11: Confusion Matrix for Training 1 (Injected)

Figure A.12: F1-confidence curve for Training 1 (Injected)

Figure A.13: Precision-confidence curve for Training 1 (Injected)

Figure A.14: Recall-confidence curve for Training 1 (Injected)

Figure A.15: Precision-Recall curve for Training 1 (Injected)

A.7 Deklaration af Generativ Kunstig Intelligens (GAI)

Deklaration af Generativ Kunstig Intelligens (GAI) i projekter

Navn: Michael Søndergaard Nørbo Madsen
Studienummer: 202202966
Projekttype: Speciale
Projekttitel: Leveraging Hierarchical Classification and Thumbnail Injection for Improved Weed and Crop Detection

Jeg har benyttet generativ kunstig intelligens til udfærdigelse af dette projekt (sæt kryds)
Beskriv hvilke GAI-værktøjer, du har benyttet (husk version):

ChatGPT: GPT-3.5
ChatGPT: GPT-4.0
ChatGPT: GPT-4o

Jeg har brugt GAI på følgende vis:

Nogle mulige anvendelsesområder er angivet som inspiration – slet eller tilføj efter behov. For hvert relevant område forklares, hvordan GAI er benyttet. Beskriv f.eks. kortfattet hvordan informationen blev genereret, samt forklar hvordan outputet er anvendt i din projektrapport.

- til at søge eller strukturere information
- til programmeringsopgaver
- til dataanalyse
- til fremstilling af figurer
- til at formatere tekst/formler i din opgave
- til at få feedback/forbedringer/korrektur på tekst og formulering
- til at generere tekst anvendt direkte i opgaven
- andet

- Forslag til alternative skrivemåder ("How can this [...] be worded differently?")
- Python plot script ("How can I plot [...] in Python?")
- Kode-hjælp generelt ("How can I add a progress-bar to this [...]?)
- Titel-generering ("Please suggest 10 potential titles for my project given this description [...]")
- SQL-query hjælp ("Can you ensure me this query [...] does NOT modify anything in the database besides [...]")
- Rapport struktur perspektiv ("What do you think about this structure for a master thesis report about [...]")
- Gøre paragraf skarpere ("Can you identify any redundancies in this text [...], if yes, why?")
- Informationssøgning ("Please describe how the YOLOv5 evaluation when running the validation command")
- Simple python filtering scripts ("Make a script to filter this from this given a file like this [...]")
- Rapport korrektur ("Please check the following text for spelling and/or grammatical errors: [...]")
- Latex command'er ("Please make a latex command for [...]")
- Sanity checks ("I have this idea [...], can you identify any pitfalls?")
- Synonymer ("Please provide me 5 synonyms for [...]")
- Foreslå akademiske vendinger ("How could this sentence [...] be worded more academically?")